

SEAS4GES: Tool Factsheets

An extract from Appendix 1 of the GES4SEAS
Deliverable 2.3: Guidelines (Best Practical Options) for
Practical Ecosystem Approach

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SEAS4GES: Tool Factsheets

The **Factsheets** of the EBA tools have been included below, providing supplementary information about the tool(s) selected when using the SEAS4GES DST. This information is intended to assist the user in making decisions on how best to proceed with the application, while considering the strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of the tools.

The factsheets are reported in tabular form, with the topic addressed in the online survey given in the first column of the table and the summary of the information obtained from the respondents in the second column. Tool identification numbers (#) are given as per main report (Franco et al., 2023). References cited in the factsheets are given at the end of this document.

The factsheets originate from the responses collected through the online questionnaire from experts on ecosystem-based approaches. Replicate responses were merged to compile all captured information about each tool. The information provided by the respondents on the elements of EBM addressed by a tool has been integrated with similar information from D2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023) for completeness. The latter also includes a score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver each addressed EBM element.

Conceptual models

Conceptual models (including mental models, mind maps, argument mapping, horrendograms, organograms, etc.) are regarded as an integral part of summarizing complex relationships within a system (e.g., natural ecosystem, socio-economic system, socio-ecological system). They aim to present graphically (visually) the main components (nodes) of a system, the pathways (vectors) linking those components and thus the nature of changes in one part of the system having repercussions for other parts of the system. They usually play an important role in communication and common understanding between developers and users. While these are often qualitative diagrams, they may form the basis of a quantitative assessment and, thus, future mathematical descriptions and predictive models. They can also draw the methodological procedures to be followed on the basis of homogenised criteria (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Conceptual models (generic tool, #1) [1 response, Expert].
- MAMBO (specific/particular tool, #1.1) [1 response, Expert].
- GES4HABs decision tree (specific/particular tool) [NOTE: information about this tool was obtained at a later stage of the Deliverable 2.3 reporting, and, therefore, it could not be included as a standalone tool in the analysis or in the current version of SEAS4GES DST. However, the information provided for this specific tool has been included as a factsheet for completeness, and it will be fully integrated in the SEAS4GES DST at a later stage].

Tool name	Conceptual models (generic tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.6) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*2) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*2.5) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*2.6) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.7) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*3) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*2.6)

Tool name	Conceptual models (generic tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*2.3) ● EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*4.2) ● EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.6) ● EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.2) ● EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.4) ● EBM13 - Climate change (*2.9) ● EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.8) ● EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*2) ● EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.8) ● EBM17 – Risks (*1.9) ● EBM18 – Other policy requirements: (*2.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plan ● Act ● Check <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional PACE management phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Conceptual models can build in the relevant concepts for the analysis and show the direction of changes, but other tools are required for quantification. They are, therefore, a starting point for most other tools and are useful in stakeholder discussions.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For EU project work ● Within EU Technical Expert Groups ● Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups ● Within ICES Working Groups ● Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG ● Delivery of monitoring programmes ● Tracking progress against action plans, etc. ● Design of remediation/management measures ● Informing decision-making ● Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development ● Development of MSFD thresholds
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>Overall, the tool is not used to assess GES Descriptors and/or Criteria.</p>

Tool name	Conceptual models (generic tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Feedback mechanisms and causal loop analysis between the elements - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Feedback mechanisms and causal loop analysis between the elements - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tool generally does not require quantitative data. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tool generally does not require semi-quantitative data. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence or absence of all components could be added to the models. <p>Being a conceptual tool, there is no need for quantitative aspects, although they can be given, even using HML scoring.</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>No spatial components required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p>
<p>Confidence/ Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. This confidence is associated with the knowledge and confidence of the user in the links between nodes and pathways.</p>

Tool name		Conceptual models (generic tool)	
Tool group		Conceptual models	
		The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.	
Other resources required		<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological knowledge • Wide ability to think out of the box and bring together features, pathways and interactions <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>	
Tool references/links		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avison D.E., Golder P.A., Shah H.U., 1992. Towards an SSM toolkit: rich picture diagramming. <i>European Journal of Information Systems</i> 1: 397-408. • Davies M., 2010. Concept mapping, mind mapping and argument mapping: what are the differences, and do they matter? <i>Higher Education</i>, 62(3), 279-301. 	
Strengths and Weaknesses			
Limitations to tool applicability		The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.	
Barriers to tool application		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The only barrier to the tool is its limited ability to consider and link the features; hence, it should be used for both brainstorming situations and climate events. 	
Overall Strengths		<p>The main strength lies in its role as a foundational tool—a starting point for any other tool. It serves to indicate the direction and application of other tools, facilitating hypothesis generation prior to hypothesis testing through alternative methods. It can be stakeholder-led, making it the initial step in scenario development and interrogation.</p> <p>The tool not only aims to consolidate existing knowledge but also highlights areas of information gaps. Its effectiveness extends to communication with lay audiences, making it a valuable instrument for conveying complex information in an accessible manner.</p>	
Overall Weaknesses		It is not designed for quantitative analysis, even if it is the starting point as such; it is not amendable to statistical testing.	

Tool name	MAMBO - Environmental Matrix for the Management of Blooms (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>The tool is not considered to address any EBM elements (and consequently any PACE management phases) in its current state because it was still under development at the time the online survey was being undertaken.</p> <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address the following EBM elements: (7, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM17 – Risks <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Once the tool is developed and in use, other tools will be required to fully deliver the above EBM elements.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is new and is not currently being used.</p> <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess GES descriptors, namely D5 (Eutrophication).
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited to use in data-rich, skills-rich situations and not suitable for data-poor, skills-poor situations. It is moderately suited to use in data-rich, but skills-poor situations or data-poor, but skills-rich situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as single variables

Tool name	MAMBO - Environmental Matrix for the Management of Blooms (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrients, phytoplankton counts, salinity. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area coverage of the bloom. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taxonomic expertise (species ID). <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components are required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. This confidence is associated with the confidence of the user in the taxonomic expertise used.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Ecological knowledge <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<p>Links to GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAMBO was developed under GES4SEAS Task 2.2 to address different Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) and their interaction with human and environmental pressures. MAMBO is embedded in a decision tree called GES4HABs. See Katsanevakis et al., 2023. GES4SEAS Deliverable 2.2. Technical report on the state-of-the-art in support of Ecosystem-Based Management approaches to address Harmful Algal Blooms, jellyfish outbreaks, invasive species, and decline of top predators.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, as it is restricted to particular ecosystem components (species groups or habitats).</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets
Overall Strengths	<p>The tool is still in development - testing it in case studies is required to consider its strengths.</p>

Tool name	MAMBO - Environmental Matrix for the Management of Blooms (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Overall Weaknesses	The tool is still in development - testing it in case studies is required to consider weaknesses.

Tool name	GES4HABs decision tree (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
<p>Uses of the tool</p>	<p>The GES4HABs decision tree defines a sequence of decision steps to identify HAB management strategies according to their state (evaluated against predefined baselines) and causes (anthropic or natural).The criteria included could also be applied for other environmental issues.</p>
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>The EBM elements considered among the decision tree nodes are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 – Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD <p>Once the tool is developed and in use, other tools will be required to fully deliver the above EBM elements.</p> <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is new and is not currently being used.</p> <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance communication and common understanding • Informing decision-making • Development of baseline thresholds • Development of appropriate indicators and thresholds • Optimization/adaptation or delivery of monitoring programmes • Delineate the framework for remediation/management measures and anticipatory and holistic approaches.
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool does not specifically prone which Descriptors and Criteria should be assessed as different ones may be relevant according to the regional nature of HABs and their associated impacts along with the existing pressures. This decision has to be made on the basis of the results of the initial assessment exercise and the analysis of pressures linked with these different types of HABs. A table with potential Descriptors and criteria that could be involved to support the managements decisions is provided in D2.2.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is a decision tree. The different decision nodes depend on the results of the interim analysis to be performed (i.e., initial assessment, thresholds and indicators, evidence for anthropic causes, etc.). Therefore, data will be required to carry out these interim procedures (not for the decision tree itself). In this sense, the quality of the data and the obtained</p>

Tool name		GES4HABs decision tree (specific/particular tool)	
Tool group		Conceptual models	
		analysis outcomes will be linked to the confidence and success of the management decisions adopted.	
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool		<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Background Knowledge and existing monitoring programmes of HAB events to support the initial assessment of HABs. <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of best options management strategies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ control and mitigation measures and surveillance monitoring, or ○ initiate also an EBM approach like MSFD to endorse more holistic management strategies, optimise/adapt/enhance monitoring programmes for HABs, and implement accountability for pressures and socio-economic impacts related with HABs. 	
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components		The tool can use expert judgement instead of data, but endorses the implementation of several analysis that require the use of data.	
Spatial and temporal scales		The tool can be used at different spatial scales (i.e., can be used by a local authority or an international organisation to address different cases of HAB events). The decision tree includes procedures and management to be implemented either at short time scales (control and mitigation measures) and multiyear time scales (assessments, thresholds, etc)	
Confidence/Uncertainty		The tool does not produce a quantitative output and thus measure of confidence/uncertainty is not part of the OUTPUTS.	
Other resources required		<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HABs types and major impacts affecting an area. • European legislation (Food regulations and environmental directives applied in the marine realms (MSFD, WFD, MSP, BWD, etc) <p>No specific software or hardware is required to apply the tool itself, although different external resources are required to implement the interim procedures and analysis requirements included as nodes)</p> <p>The decision tree includes another conceptual matrix decision tool (MAMBO) described below.</p>	
Tool references/links		<p>Links to GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GES4HABs was developed under GES4SEAS Task 2.2 See Katsanevakis et al., 2023. GES4SEAS Deliverable 2.2. Technical report on the state-of-the-art in support of Ecosystem-Based Management approaches to address Harmful Algal Blooms, jellyfish outbreaks, invasive species, and decline of top predators. 	
Strengths and Weaknesses			
Limitations to tool applicability			
Barriers to tool application		A basic understanding of what HAB events are, and the concepts and semantics of European legislation (Food regulations and environmental directives applied in the marine realms (MSFD, WFD, MSP, BWD, etc) are required to understand the decision tree flow.	
Overall Strengths		The decision tree has been elaborated and agreed by a quite large (around 20) group of experts working on HABs. These experts include partners from GES4SEAS partners and invited experts from ACTNOW project and external invited experts).	

Tool name	GES4HABs decision tree (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Overall Weaknesses	The tool has still not been used, nor tested by users. It would be useful to evaluate the users experience and feedback (i.e., on ease of concept and flow understanding, perceived semantic quality and clarity, etc)

Semi-quantitative mental models – Fuzzy cognitive mapping

Semi-quantitative mental models represent a progression beyond conceptual models, as they not only document the connections between nodes (the primary components of the system) but also specify the direction and strength of interactions. This enables straightforward exploration of scenarios. Given the complexity of systems such as natural ecosystems, socioeconomic systems, and socio-ecological systems, these models serve as simplifications, valuable for enhancing shared understanding and communication. They are particularly beneficial when working with stakeholders, helping to identify common understanding, goals and objectives, and highlighting differences in perspective, values and priorities (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool, #2.1) [3 responses, Very familiar].

Tool name	Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 – Other policy requirements:

Tool name	Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plan ● Act ● Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is not able to address additional EBM elements or additional PACE management phases.</p> <p>According to 2 of the responses (in a total of 3), other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. FCM has limited quantitative aspects, delivering an average general opinion based on qualitative data. To fully deliver any EBM element, quantitative data are also needed. FCM can indicate what elements and (type of) interactions are important in an area. The tool is very useful for scoping issues (e.g., with stakeholders, policy-makers, etc.) in the Plan stage (of PACE), and for identifying linkages and interdependencies in the Act stage - and can be used for some scenario analysis/trade-off identification where data are lacking. Where data are available, these methods should complement more quantitative approaches.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For EU project work ● Within ICES Working Groups ● Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Informing decision-making ● Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	Most responses (67%) indicated that FCM is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria. The models are built according to the specific needs of the user, so they can be tailored to any of the descriptors or criteria (e.g., D1, D3).
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Activities - as multiple variables ● Pressures - as multiple variables ● Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables ● Responses or management measures - as multiple variables

Tool name	Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy/governance decisions (e.g., MPAs, Landing Obligation, Brexit, etc.) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated (usually qualitatively). However, it is good to derive the relationships between variables from quantitative data. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated (usually qualitatively). However, it is good to derive the relationships between variables from quantitative data. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the importance of factor (= variable) and/or vectors (= interaction between variables) following a Likert scaling. The majority of models are built on qualitative data using expert and/or stakeholder knowledge. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components are required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Statistical • Ecological knowledge • Communication skills • Social, Economic and Governance System knowledge • Familiarity with building conceptual models • Experience with running workshops, stakeholder engagement and facilitating such exercises <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (Mental Modeler). Alternatively, the gathering of data and analysis can also be carried out without software.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • www.mentalmodeler.org • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=By24uhIbBn4 • Gray S., Zanre E., Gray S., 2013. Fuzzy Cognitive Maps as representations of mental models and group beliefs: theoretical and technical issues. In Fuzzy Cognitive maps for Applied Sciences and Engineering - From fundamentals to extensions and learning algorithms Ed: Elpiniki I. Papageorgiou. Springer Publishing

Tool name	Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	While most (67%) of the responses reported that the tool makes no specific assumptions, and should be widely applicable, one response indicated that there are assumptions deriving from the collaborative environmental management context where FCMs are generally applied. The determination of expert credibility is not always straightforward, and often one's expertise is not directly correlated with the quality of one's mental model.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • The tool does not require focus groups to be applied, but these will increase the relevance/usefulness of the resulting models
Overall Strengths	FCM is very flexible and easy to learn and can be used and adapted to most situations (social, economic, ecological), making it especially relevant for scoping complex questions. It is an excellent first step for many analyses (especially in multi-disciplinary groups and/or with stakeholders), and it can be carried out with all types of audiences, from skilled policy makers to practitioners or laymen. Its effectiveness lies in its ability to pinpoint issues and improve communication among stakeholders. It also enables the evaluation of potential policy options prior to their implementation and helps identify crucial gaps in knowledge that may affect the reliability of model predictions. The tool can also be coupled with outputs from other analyses (e.g., risk assessment) to elaborate interlinkages between elements, or to describe system understanding (very relevant for cumulative effects) to identify knowledge gaps and direct research effort.
Overall Weaknesses	The data used to build the model is often based on opinions which may deviate from facts. The tool is limited in what it can achieve on its own. During the verification stage of the participatory modelling, one of the potential drawbacks is the challenge of motivating stakeholders to thoroughly verify the accuracy of their models.

Knowledge Graphs

A knowledge graph is a structured representation of knowledge that encapsulates information on entities, their attributes, and the relationships between them. It consists of ‘nodes’ (representing entities) and ‘edges’ (representing the relationships between them) and can be visualized as a network or a graph. It is a type of information source that is used by search engines and other applications to provide more relevant and accurate information to users. A knowledge graph might be usefully viewed as a combination of a graphical network diagram allied to a database providing information on each of the nodes and links (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Knowledge Graphs (generic tool, #3) [1 response, Very familiar].
- Knowledge Graphs - proprietary system custom built for EAD (based on DAPSI(W)R(M)) (specific/particular tool, #3.1) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs (generic tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*1.4) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*1.4) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*1.2) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*4.8) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.6) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*4.6) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.6) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*1) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.6) • EBM13 - Climate change (*3.4) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*3) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*0.8)

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs (generic tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EBM18 – Other policy requirements (*2.8) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plan <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional PACE management phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Act <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements, as knowledge graphs are not fully-fledged intervention tools.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Within the context of sub-national regulatory authority <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Informing decision-making ● Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>Knowledge Graphs are not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited to use in data-rich, skills-rich situations and not suitable for data-poor, skills-poor situations. It is moderately suited to use in data-rich, but skills-poor situations or data-poor, but skills-rich situations.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Activities - as multiple variables ● Pressures - as multiple variables ● Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables ● Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Activities - as single variables ● Pressures - as single variables ● Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables ● Responses or management measures - as multiple variables

Tool name		Knowledge Graphs (generic tool)	
Tool group		Knowledge Graphs	
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated. <p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>		
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). No temporal components are produced.</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) 		
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS, as entries are manually tagged as to the level of confidence.</p>		
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is readily available, but there are associated purchase and/or licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>		
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Penev L., Dimitrova M., Senderov V., Zhelezov G., Georgiev T., Stoev P., Simov K., 2019. Openbiodiv: a knowledge graph for literature-extracted linked open data in biodiversity science, <i>Publications</i>, 7(2), 38. • Babalou S., Zander F., Kleinstauber E., El Haoui B., Schellenberger Costa D., Kattge J., Konig-Ries B., 2022. iKNOW- A Knowledge Graph Management Platform for the Biodiversity Domain, <i>Biodiversity Information Science and Standards</i>, 6. 		
Strengths and Weaknesses			
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability, as it assumes the DAPSIWRM framework.		
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets 		
Overall Strengths	It is a System approach.		
Overall Weaknesses	Requires a degree of knowledge of systems.		

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs - proprietary system custom built for EAD (based on DAPSI(W)R(M)) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (15, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional PACE management phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Knowledge Graphs - EAD DAPSI(W)R(M) is intended to document the state of knowledge and hence, knowledge gaps. Once populated with concepts, the system could be used as a schema for modelling real-world instances of EBM concepts. The system does not hard code any thematic constraints - therefore, it can handle any thematic system provided it can be defined in terms of cause-effect. However, that knowledge must first be added.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emirate of Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs - proprietary system custom built for EAD (based on DAPSI(W)R(M)) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Human needs and wants as Drivers and Complementary Capital as Enabler of Activities - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Human needs and wants as Drivers and Complementary Capital as Enabler of Activities - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. The current system works at the concept level. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. The current system works at the concept level. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. The current system works at the concept level. <p>The system currently works with generic EBM concepts. The concepts and inter-concept relationships could be used as a schema for representing real systems and thus provide a framework for scenario modelling.</p> <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does produce a measure of use confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological knowledge

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs - proprietary system custom built for EAD (based on DAPSI(W)R(M)) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental systems knowledge (from all environmental domains) as well (high level) knowledge of socio-economic systems which interface with the natural environment <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is currently proprietary and not readily available. It may be made freely available in future.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	The software is proprietary – contact derek.gliddon@ead.gov.ae for more information.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The subject system is a knowledge organisation and research planning tool, and not an operational EBM decision-making.
Overall Strengths	It is designed to capture and share "State-of-knowledge" for an environmental system for a specific jurisdiction/region. It is based on an extended DAPSIWRM cause-effect framework. It takes a holistic and integrated earth-systems approach, accumulating cause-effect knowledge from multiple disciplines and sectors. It has the potential to develop a knowledge schema that could be used to define a holistic network of models.
Overall Weaknesses	The system was not designed in response to the needs of the European policy context. The current system works at the concept/meta-level. It develops holistic, multi-disciplinary, multi-sectoral frameworks that could be used to organise/interoperate data-driven models of DAPSIWRM concepts and their cause-effect connections.

BBN probabilistic models

Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs) are models that graphically and probabilistically represent correlative and causal relationships among variables and that account for uncertainty. BBNs are based on two structural elements: (1) a directed acyclic graph (DAG) showing dependencies among variables (nodes), and (2) conditional probability tables indicating link strengths in the graph. The DAG comprises variables representing the modelled system, connected by arrows denoting cause-and-effect relations and showcasing statistical dependencies. A lack of a link indicates statistical independence. There are no feedback paths from child to parent nodes. The DAG can be expert-designed or learned empirically, forming the basis for operational BBNs. Each node features a probability distribution representing uncertainty about its state, either continuous or discrete. The sum of state values in the probability distribution equals 1. BBNs are effective for integrating diverse data types and modelling complex systems with numerous uncertain variables (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- BBN probabilistic models (generic tool, #4) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	BBN probabilistic models (generic tool)
Tool group	BBN probabilistic models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>The tool is not currently designed to address any EBM elements (and consequently any PACE management phases) because it needs to be tailored to the specific analysis required. This, in turn, will determine which EBM elements the tool can address.</p> <p>D2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023) identified the tool to deliver the following EBM elements (with a score > 4, as per Table 27 of 2.1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address the following EBM elements: (7, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs)

Tool name	BBN probabilistic models (generic tool)
Tool group	BBN probabilistic models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM16 - Uncertainty <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>The tool, by itself, is able to fully deliver against the requirements of the above EBM elements. BBN probabilistic models are statistical models that can be tailored to a wide range of analyses of complex relationships.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups <p>The tool is not relevant to marine governance.</p>
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>BBN models can be tailored to assess any of the GES descriptors or criteria.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is generally well-suited to use in skills-rich situations and poorly or not suitable in skills-poor situations (data-rich, but skills-poor situations and data-poor, skills-poor situations, respectively).</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For GES or CEA: Spatiotemporal data of criteria, activities or pressures are needed for spatial explicit assessments of effects and future change. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any data - the uncertainty depends on the spread of probability distributions. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any data - the uncertainty depends on the spread of probability distributions. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>

Tool name	BBN probabilistic models (generic tool)
Tool group	BBN probabilistic models
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>No spatial components are required. Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>The models do not require/produce any spatial or temporal inputs/outputs, but they can handle spatial and temporal data depending on the question addressed and the data available.</p>
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. All results are expressed as probabilities of a certain state or outcome.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs. For example, R software can be used. NETICA is an alternative commercial software.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
<p>Tool references/links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NETICA: https://www.norsys.com/tutorials/netica/nt_toc_A.htm • GeNIe: https://www.bayesfusion.com/genie/ • HUGIN: https://www.hugin.com/ • Stelzenmüller V., Lee J., Garnacho E., Rogers S.I., 2010. Assessment of a Bayesian Belief Network-GIS framework as a practical tool to support marine planning. <i>Marine Pollution Bulletin</i> 60: 1743-1754. • Pihlajamäki M., Helle I., Haapasaari P., Sarkki S., Kuikka S., Lehtikoinen A., 2020. Catching the future: Applying Bayesian belief networks to exploratory scenario storylines to assess long-term changes in Baltic herring (<i>Clupea harengus membras</i>, Clupeidae) and salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i>, Salmonidae) fisheries. <i>Fish and Fisheries</i> 21, 797–812. <p>Links with GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under Task 3.4, capacity-building activities for BBNs are being organised.

Tool name		BBN probabilistic models (generic tool)
Tool group		BBN probabilistic models
Strengths and Weaknesses		
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, as all relationships between components are derived directly from data, interviews, or expert knowledge.	
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires focus groups to be applied <p>In this case, focus groups refer to expert groups. In a GES or Cumulative Effects Assessment (CEA) context, the specified relationships, which are not based on data, are usually derived from expert workshops or collaborative approaches.</p>	
Overall Strengths	It can integrate spatiotemporal data with semi-quantitative and qualitative data.	
Overall Weaknesses	It requires skills to understand the statistics and related outcomes.	

Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability

Risk assessment and risk management techniques (for example, using the ISO standard Bow-tie analysis) such as IEC/ISO 31010 (IEC/ISO, 2009) are fundamental to industrial and commercial applications and have only since 2010 been applied to environmental challenges. Bow-tie diagrams are a visual tool describing and analysing the pathways of a risk, from hazards to outcomes and reviewing controls (preventative and mitigation/compensation methods, the so-called Programmes of Measures). The approach shows the causes of a problem (to the left of the knot of a Bow-tie), the hazard and element of main concern (the knot of a Bow-tie) and the consequences of a hazard happening (to the right of the knot). Various controls can be placed on the left of the hazard to prevent the hazard from occurring, or on the right to reduce/mitigate/compensate for the magnitude of any consequences (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool, #5) [1 response, Expert].
- Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool, #5.1) [2 responses, Expert].

Tool name	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*3.8) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*2.1) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*2.3) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*2.4) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*3.3) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*3) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1.9) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1.9) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*4.5) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*3.5) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.5)

Tool name	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.9) • EBM13 - Climate change (*2.7) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*4.3) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*1.9) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*2.6) • EBM17 – Risks (*4.7) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*3.8) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional PACE management phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • In policy development <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development • To analyse, evaluate and implement appropriate measures
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	Overall, this tool group is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally moderately suited/well-suited to all data/skills situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables

Tool name	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequencies of activities, spatial and temporal extent of pressures, and probabilities of effects <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequencies of activities, spatial and temporal extent of pressures, and probabilities of effects <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequencies of activities, spatial and temporal extent of pressures, and probabilities of effects <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). No spatial components are produced.</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). No temporal components are produced.</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g. seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years)
Confidence/ Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Modelling • Ecological knowledge

Tool name	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEC31010: https://www.iso.org/standard/72140.html • WIND-ERA: https://aztidata.es/wind-era/; Galparsoro, I., I. Menchaca, J. M. Garmendia, Á. Borja, A. D. Maldonado, G. Iglesias, J. Bald, 2022. Reviewing the ecological impacts of offshore wind farms. <i>npj Ocean Sustainability</i>, 1:1 • WEC-ERA: https://aztidata.es/wec-era/; Galparsoro, I., M. Korta, I. Subirana, Á. Borja, I. Menchaca, O. Solaun, I. Muxika, G. Iglesias, J. Bald, 2021. A new framework and tool for ecological risk assessment of wave energy converters projects. <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i>, 151: 111539
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	No, the tool makes no specific assumptions, and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It lacks the policy scope, context and criteria, as well as the expected outcomes of the management measures <p>These barriers may be overcome by including the managers who have to use these tools and not policy developers.</p>
Overall Strengths	It is a good quality management approach typically found in other management standards, such as ISO9000.
Overall Weaknesses	It is not designed to identify, analyse, evaluate, and ultimately treat risks through the programme of measures to achieve GES.

Tool name	Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM16 - Uncertainty <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Bow tie analysis is valuable for outlining all the components and their interconnections. The tool is primarily qualitative, represented as a visual, but it would be enhanced if quantified by incorporating probabilities, allowing for its expansion into a BBN probabilistic model. The tool has utility in bringing together all elements of the socio-ecological system within EBM and can be informed by stakeholder input.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p>

Tool name	Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The Bow-tie analysis could be applied to assess any GES descriptor or criteria. For example, the descriptors could serve either as the starting point (causes of change) or the consequences. For instance, descriptors like fishing (D3), pollution (D8, D10), contaminants in food (D9), etc., could be inserted as causes, while others such as biodiversity (D1) or seabed integrity (D6) could be defined as consequences.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited to use in skills-rich situations, and the suitability is lower in skill-poor situations (moderately suitable).</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amounts of factors that cause a change and the links from this to amounts of consequences; number of response measures that are available and any quantitative conditions for those responses. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amounts of factors that cause a change and the links from this to amounts of consequences; number of response measures that are available and any quantitative conditions for those responses.

Tool name	
Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool)	
Tool group	
Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability	
	<p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any activities, pressures, receptors and management measures information. Qualitative indications of causes and consequences. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p> <p>The tool does not require spatial or temporal data, but these can be used depending on the question addressed and the data available. The qualitative inputs can be links between variables, causes, consequences, etc., without being time series, maps, etc. However, the output from that time series or map analysis would give the links in the Bow-tie, and perhaps the magnitude of causes and consequences.</p>
Confidence/ Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS, to the extent that the user should understand the likelihood of the causes of a particular problem.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS, to the extent that the user should understand the likelihood of a set of consequences and the ability of prevention and mitigation to address these.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modelling Ecological knowledge Understanding the concept of bow tie analysis <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is readily available, but there are associated purchase and/or licence costs (BowTieXP). It can be obtained short term with not associated costs for education and research. However, Network diagrams in R can be a valid and effective alternative to apply the tool, or, ultimately, Bow-tie analysis can be done using power-point or any other drawing package.</p> <p>Additional resources needed can include flip charts, etc., when used in stakeholder engagement situations.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proprietary software with training - https://www.wolterskluwer.com/en/solutions/enablon/bowtie Cormier, R., Elliott, M. and Rice, J., 2019. Putting on a bow-tie to sort out who does what and why in the complex arena of marine policy and management. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i>, 648, pp.293-305. Cormier, R., Elliott, M., and Kannen, A. 2018. IEC/ISO Bow-tie analysis of marine legislation: A case study of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. ICES Cooperative Research Report No. 342. 56 pp.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	There are no real barriers to tool application other than recognising its limitations and its level of application (it can be applied conceptually or

Tool name	Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	highly-qualitatively). One response indicated that when working with stakeholders, it might be helpful not to mention the tool, as some stakeholders become too centred on the tool and less focussed on the inputs/outputs.
Overall Strengths	It is an ISO-approved system, used by the industry to look at the cause-consequence & response chain and related to hazard and risk in both industrial and environmental concerns. It can be used with and without proprietary software and should be flexible. It can be used by and with stakeholders. It has the ability to link all the relevant aspects and fully fits the DAPSI(W)R(M) approach. The consequence from one analysis can become the cause for the next. It is flexible and can cover many elements. Ultimately, it is a visual representation of linkages, providing a convenient way to quickly sketch out connections.
Overall Weaknesses	It can become complex and may call for chained, parallel or serial bow-ties to be created. It can seem daunting for users and, therefore, requires guidance during application. Bow-tie XP is expensive and has very limited export functions. Using the bow-tie analysis in further work is a headache. While Visio and PowerPoint are acceptable, they can be time-consuming and, therefore, costly in terms of staff time. Sketching on paper and then using it to build a network diagram is a good compromise. Building the diagram in R means that further analysis can be easily done.

Cumulative impact spatial mapping

The global human impact assessment outlined by Halpern et al. (2008) is a spatial assessment (using a grid with a defined resolution for all spatial data) that includes (i) spatial layers representing pressures, (ii) spatial layers for ecosystem components (such as species, species groups, habitats), and (iv) weight scores that indicate the sensitivity of ecosystem components to each pressure (various methods exist for determining these weight scores). Depending on the specific application, the three scores obtained from the different layers may be summed, or the mean of impacted ecosystem components is calculated (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool, #6) [7 responses; 5 Expert, 2 Very Familiar].
- CIMPAL - Cumulative impact of invasive alien species (specific/particular tool, #6.1) [1 response, Expert].
- PlanWise4Blue (specific/particular tool, #6.2) [1 response, Very familiar].

Tool name		Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group		Cumulative impact spatial mapping
Uses of the tool		
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*4.7) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*2.6) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*2.7) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*1.7) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*1.7) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.8) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*4) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*3.8) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*3.1) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.3) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*0.9) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*1.9) 	

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.9) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.1) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*2.6) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.5) • EBM17 – Risks (*2.5) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.6) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>According to a majority (57%) of respondents, additional tools are necessary to fully address the EBM elements mentioned above. While cumulative impact spatial mapping assesses potential activity-pressure effects, it falls short in determining the status and distance-to-target, confidence, and the identification of tipping points and thresholds of pressures resulting from multiple activities. Moreover, some EBM elements require the use of additional tools such as GIS, Species Distribution Modelling, and Statistical Modelling, especially when incorporating a risk-based approach, sensu Stelzenmüller et al. (2018). Cumulative impact spatial mapping can be easily adapted for various assessment purposes, including those related to the MSFD, MSPD, ecosystem services and more, or for evaluating the underlying causes of potential impacts. For example, Tools4MSP are a set of web and open-source tools developed to support the implementation of Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), with a specific emphasis on the analysis of conflicts between marine uses and the analysis of cumulative impacts (CI) of human activities on marine environments. The Cumulative Effects Assessment tool aims to facilitate the MSP process within an Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) by assessing the potential cumulative impacts of maritime activities on the marine environment. Another example described the French case, where the "strong protection" requirements for MPAs entail measures that significantly reduce or eliminate human pressures. Cumulative impact spatial mapping helps to identify where activities and pressures are threatening marine ecosystems. This information, when combined with systematic planning tools like MARXAN or Prioritizr, assists in identifying locations for high protection areas effectively.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within other National Competent Authorities • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within ICES Working Groups <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development • Pressure indicators development • Assess the effectiveness of Programmes of Measures
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>29% of the responses indicated that the tool group is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria. 14% of the responses indicated that the tool can only assess descriptors, while 14% reported that the tool can only assess criteria. 43% of the responses reported that the tool group can assess both descriptors and criteria.</p> <p>Examples of GES descriptors and criteria that the tool is able to assess:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2C3, e.g., through the application of the CIMPAL index, which is a cumulative impacts spatial mapping tool (Katsanevakis et al. 2016) - CIMPAL is recommended for this criterion by Tsiamis et al. (2021) • D6 (Seafloor integrity); D6C1; D6C2; D6C3; D6C4; D6C5 • D7 (hydrographical changes); D7C1; D7C2 • D8C4; D8C2
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich situations. According to most of the responses, skills become relevant when applying the tool in data-poor situations. At least 1 response has reported that the tool is well-suited for all situations.</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No mandatory quantitative data, but quantitative input data is preferred. Pressure intensity in space (and time), ecosystem components (e.g., densities) and ecosystem components sensitivity/vulnerability. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All inputs can be semi-quantitative (using indices) if quantitative is missing. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All inputs can be qualitative if better data is missing (e.g., Low/Medium/High abundance, minimal/minor/moderate/major/massive vulnerability, presence/absence). <p>The tool is a spatial tool, and the input/output layers can be of any quality. It requires spatial distribution of ecological features of interest and of pressures (ideally quantitative, e.g., abundance, coverage, but also semi-quantitative (indices) or qualitative).</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>Temporal data are not required for the approach, but it can be used to produce temporal outputs, which is a current research direction.</p>

Tool name	
Tool group	
Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)	
Cumulative impact spatial mapping	
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>Most of the responses (57%) reported that the tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The uncertainty is assessed by estimating the quality of data, methodological approach, indicator used, etc. See Stock et al. (2016) and Stelzenmüller et al. (2018) for examples and recommendations for accounting for uncertainty. One response also mentioned that the R-coded versions of the cumulative impact mapping software could use uncertainty in input maps and impact weight scores.</p> <p>Most of the responses (57%) reported that the tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. The tool may include a general uncertainty analysis integrated with the cumulative impact assessment. It can generate a map of high and low confidence on cumulative impact using a Monte Carlo simulation.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Statistical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>To apply the tool, no specific software is required. However, there are freely available software with no licence costs (e.g., EcoImpactMapper, Tools4MSP).</p> <p>Additional resources needed include GIS software.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://figshare.com/articles/code/ImpactMapper/1519342 • https://geoplatform.tools4msp.eu/ • Stock, A., 2016. Open source software for mapping human impacts on marine ecosystems with an additive model. <i>Journal of Open Research Software</i>, 4(1). • Halpern B. S., Walbridge S., Selkoe K. A., Kappel C. V., Micheli F., D'Agrosa C., Bruno J.F., Casey K.S., Ebert C., Fox H.E., Fujita R., Heinemann D., Lenihan H.S., Madin E.M.P., Perry M.T., Selig E.R., Spalding M., Steneck R., Watson R., 2008. A global map of human impact on marine ecosystems. <i>Science</i> 319, 948–952. <p>Links with GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under GES4SEAS WP4, work is underway on cumulative impact spatial mapping (with the development of the GES4SEAS toolbox). The aim is to bridge the main weaknesses of the current tools and create linkages and synergies with the SCAIRM tool for impact risk ranking, as well as improving the linkages with ecosystem services (i.e., how multiple pressures affect the capacity of ecosystem services delivery).
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>All responses indicated that the tool makes assumptions, but 57% reported that these don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability, while the remaining reported that the assumptions may potentially affect or restrict the applicability of the tool in some way.</p>

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<p>Two assumptions can be considered restrictive: all the impacts are additive, and the pressure-impact relationship is linear. There are also other assumptions that may affect the outcome: the fewer input data layers are added, the more the impact weight scores influence the outcome; and the temporal factor is poorly managed and may cause unnecessary noise in the output. When data are coarse or not quantitative, then an assumption must be made as to the spatial extent or intensity of, e.g., pressure data. Sensitivities of specific environmental components could be highly site-specific. Additionally, modelling pressures from human activities may involve some degree of approximation.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More funding should be allocated for systematic data collection in data-poor situations; • The application of the tool should be integrated with a monitoring field sampling to effectively assess how ecosystem components respond to multiple pressures; • Use of local expert opinion; • The uncertainty of different levels of spatial and temporal resolution should be estimated, as well as of the different data sources; • If pressure weighting scores are used, then these should be estimated by several groups of experts.
Overall Strengths	<p>Cumulative impact analyses offer an integrated assessment method for evaluating human impact on marine biodiversity. They facilitate mapping multiple pressures and identification of hotspots and dominating pressures. This approach is effective for broad-scale assessments, accommodating not only quantitative but also semi-quantitative or qualitative data. Geospatial datasets can be generated at various scales, emphasising the importance of supporting multi-scale spatial resolution analyses.</p> <p>The method provides valuable information on the spatial distribution of activities, pressures, and impact and this information can be utilized for management decisions, assisting in determining particular activities, areas, or ecological components. Additionally, it helps exploring how planned measures may affect cumulative impact (either decrease or increase). The outputs are easily understandable for policymakers, allowing straightforward prioritization of locations or specific pressures for management actions.</p> <p>Overall, this method can summarize potential impacts at any spatial scale, spanning from all human activities to any ecosystem component (or all). Successful comparisons with monitoring data provide evidence that the predictions of the tool are useful.</p> <p>As an example of a tool that has most of the characteristics indicated for the tool group, the approach of Tools4MSP is particularly flexible. It incorporates a multi-objective toolset (CEA and MUC) extendable for various</p>

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	analysis purposes. It enables the management and treatment of different datasets and formats and provides different levels of usability.
Overall Weaknesses	<p>The linkages between most pressures and their environmental effects rely on sensitivity scores set by experts. There is low accuracy in estimating uncertainty. Commonly, there is high uncertainty in cause-effect relationships, which reduces confidence in Cumulative Effects Assessments. Improved uncertainty analysis is essential to better identify data gaps. Difficulties in the parameterization of the model have led to the implementation of an additive and linear model. However, ongoing research in cumulative assessment demonstrates the need for the integration of mitigative and antagonistic effects in the pressure-environmental components interaction. Therefore, the assumption of additive effects, commonly applied, is often unrealistic. Pressure impacts are treated as being linear, while sigmoidal or logarithmic responses are sometimes more realistic.</p> <p>The tool does not rely on the true state of ecosystem components and, therefore, cannot provide thresholds or tipping points. It requires high-resolution data for local-scale assessment.</p>

Tool name	CIMPAL - Cumulative impact of invasive alien species (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. CIMPAL provides spatial explicit assessment and allows to integrate species model predictions supporting scenarios testing (e.g., manager effectiveness, climate change). However, it does not consider all the elements of the natural ecosystems, as well as other EBM elements such as stakeholders, management scenarios, etc. It can be used together with Species Distribution Models for simulations.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures

Tool name	CIMPAL - Cumulative impact of invasive alien species (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>CIMPAL is able to assess both GES descriptors and criteria.</p> <p>Examples: D2C1, D2C2, D2C3.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich situations and moderately suited for data-poor situations. Skills are less relevant when applying the tool.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geo-referenced species occurrence, habitat distribution, species-specific dispersion radius. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species-habitat specific impacts weights. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species pathways of introduction. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The uncertainty associated with the strength of evidence of the species-habitat impact weight is accounted for, and the magnitude of the impact can be downgraded accordingly. This is used to generate two CIMPAL scores: the CIMPAL precautionary approach and the CIMPAL uncertainty-averse strategy. Also, the species point occurrence has a 25-meters uncertainty</p>

Tool name	CIMPAL - Cumulative impact of invasive alien species (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<p>buffer, and a species dispersion radius based on species-specific mobility traits is also defined.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. A confidence map can be generated based on the differences between the two CIMPAL approaches (the CIMPAL precautionary approach and the CIMPAL uncertainty-averse strategy).</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>Additional resources needed include GIS software to open and explore the outputs (e.g., TIFF and CSV files).</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access the LifeWatch IJI Biotope workflow and register at https://www.lifewatch.eu/internal-joint-initiative/workflows/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. The tool is specifically designed for non-indigenous species but apart from that, it should be widely applicable.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets <p>The CIMPAL tool is a cumulative assessment tool, and therefore, it provides a cumulative score that has no ceiling. In this sense, it is suitable for tracking trends but highly dependent on the context of application and on the baseline knowledge gathered for a given assessment, context, or region.</p>
Overall Strengths	<p>The CIMPAL index is a framework for mapping the Cumulative IMPact of invasive ALien species. Computes negative impacts of invasive species on any environment, providing an overall cumulative impact map identifying areas at risk, hotspots of invasions and habitats according to their vulnerability. It ranks species according to their level of threat, supporting prioritisation of sites and species, and main pathways of introduction for management.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>A key weakness is the amount of different types of data requirements.</p>

Tool name	
PlanWise4Blue (specific/particular tool)	
Tool group	
Cumulative impact spatial mapping	
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM13 – Climate change • EBM18.2 - Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives • EBM 18.3 - Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy <p>The tool is able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making

Tool name	PlanWise4Blue (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>PlanWise4Blue is able to assess both GES descriptors and criteria.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1 (Biodiversity) • D2 (Non-indigenous species) • D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish) • D5 (Eutrophication) • D7 (Hydrographical changes) • D8 (Contaminants in the environment) • D9 (Contaminants in seafood) • D11 (Underwater noise)
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich situations and moderately suited for data-poor situations. Skills are less relevant when applying the tool.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial/temporal data of habitat conditions, multiple pressures (actual or theoretical). <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial/temporal data of habitat conditions, multiple pressures (actual or theoretical). <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial/temporal data of habitat conditions, multiple pressures (actual or theoretical). <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>

Tool name	PlanWise4Blue (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. The results are expressed with confidence limits, the range of which is dependent on the quality of input data and empirical knowledge.</p>
Other resources required	<p>No specific expertise is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://gis.sea.ee/planwise4blue
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability; namely, results are scale-dependent.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data. <p>Suggestions to overcome the barrier identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some criteria need increased empirical knowledge to reduce reliance on expert opinion.
Overall Strengths	<p>PlanWise4Blue is a freely-available user-friendly geoportal that combines novel spatial modelling of environmental background (e.g., maps of benthic habitats) with spatial data related to marine resources with an emphasis on fishery, shipping and energy. Freely available, its algorithm is based on continuous layers of nature assets data and impacts based on empirical data. The tool assesses cumulative impacts - both positive and negative - of multiple pressures, both actual and theoretical.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>Some impacts depend largely on expert opinion. Additional empirical data is continuously being incorporated to reduce this reliance.</p>

Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks

An assessment methodology developed, e.g., in ODEMM and AQUACROSS projects, tracing sector–pressure–ecosystem component pressure pathways (also known as ‘linkage chains’) and scoring them through expert judgement and data where available. The approach consists of two main steps, identifying where linkages exist (mapping in a ‘linkage matrix’) and then scoring each linkage that does occur for a number of attributes (e.g., spatial overlap, temporal overlap, degree of impact, resilience or resistance, although there are variations on these) (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool, #7) [3 responses; 2 Expert, 1 Familiar].
- SCAIRM (specific/particular tool, #7.1) [1 response, Expert].
- ODEMM (specific/particular tool, #7.2) [2 responses; 1 Expert, 1 Very familiar].
- Aquacross (specific/particular tool, #7.3) [1 response, Very familiar].
- ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (specific/particular tool, #7.4) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*4.1) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*1.9) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*3.2) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*2) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.3) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*3) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*3.1) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*2.9) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*4.8) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.8) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.2)

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*1.7) • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.6) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*3.3) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*1.3) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.6) • EBM17 – Risks (*3.9) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.8) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks is essentially a first screening tool to identify main human activities, pressures induced and ecosystem components impacted. It functions as a tool for a broad risk assessment, identifying risk hotspots by assessing the overlap of the presence of components with activities and pressures. This approach is semi-quantitative and can be subsequently employed in conjunction with specific modelling tools within a given context. However, it has limitations in terms of real spatial extent and lacks essential spatial and geospatial elements. Therefore, other tools are needed, including those that facilitate the spatial representation of information. Additionally, complementary indicators for different components along the linkage chains are also necessary.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors, although the responses diverged. One response considered that the tool is not able to assess descriptors or criteria, while another response indicated that the tool is able to assess both descriptors and criteria. All descriptors can be assessed by the tool to some</p>

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	extent, but it is particularly effective for D1 (Biodiversity) and D6 (Sea-floor integrity).
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any quantitative data available for any activity, pressure and state/impact, although not strictly required (gross estimates will work). Once the relevant links between components are established, it is possible to quantify them if proper indicators (e.g., pressures, state change, etc.) are available. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valuation of some components (if not all) can be semi-quantitative (like categorical data), e.g., the specific Activity-Pressure-Ecosystem component chain characterisation, or Ecosystem Services expert-based valuation. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several (if not all) components, pressures and activities, but this would provide only limited evidence, ultimately only the identification of presence/absence of relevant links between components. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	No spatial components are required.

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<p>Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>The approach often uses spatial maps of activities and pressures to evaluate pressures and temporal information for some or all of the year. Outputs are not mapped but could be in forecast mode. Temporal dimension can be included depending on the type of data available; if so, temporal outputs are also possible.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The input information may have associated uncertainty, such as weighting/marking expert knowledge on input variables. One response reported a 5-level score based on data support, considering factors like whether the data is from the study region or not, part of a data series or not, and whether it was published peer-review or not.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (spreadsheet software).</p> <p>Additional resources needed include GIS software or R if the information is to be spatialised.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedreschi D., Niiranen S., Skern-Mauritzen M., Reid D.G., 2023. Operationalising ODEMM risk assessment for Integrated Ecosystem Assessment scoping: Complexity vs. manageability. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i>, 9, 2766. • Borgwardt, F., Robinson, L., Trauner, D., Teixeira, H., Nogueira, A.J., Lillebø, A.I., Piet, G., Kuemmerlen, M., O'Higgins, T., McDonald, H. and Arevalo-Torres, J., 2019. Exploring variability in environmental impact risk from human activities across aquatic ecosystems. <i>Science of the total environment</i>, 652, pp.1396-1408

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teixeira, H., Lillebø, A.I., Culhane, F., Robinson, L., Trauner, D., Borgwardt, F., Kummerlen, M., Barbosa, A., McDonald, H., Funk, A. and O'higgins, T., 2019. Linking biodiversity to ecosystem services supply: Patterns across aquatic ecosystems. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i>, 657, pp.517-534.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. These assumptions are generally related to pressures, to linking the frequency of pressures to impacts without really looking at the intensity of pressures.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No monitoring data available The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements It requires focus groups to be applied It does not have any associated thresholds or targets <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some barriers can be overcome by revisiting the input categories bands (e.g., extent overlap % categories, less gross spatial overlap categories) and working further on the method to be more compatible with policy requirements. However, a major issue is posed by the lack of geospatial information (there is a risk from the overlap of a component from a pressure, but the location within the system is unknown, and, therefore, it is uncertain whether it is in an area with other risk hotspots or not). It requires assembling a group of experts across a range of disciplines - it would be possible, but not recommendable, to apply the method with only 2 or 3 experts. While it cannot really produce thresholds, targets could be something along the lines of "reducing risks".
Overall Strengths	It is a comprehensive risk assessment tool that considers all factors and provides the top impact risk combinations. Establishing linkage chains that connect human activities (A), associated pressures (P), ecosystem components (Ec) they impact, and the services (ESS) and functions (EF) they perform, it offers a thorough overview of all interacting elements. This approach effectively captures the big picture and enables the construction of scenarios to support EBM. The tool is capable of evaluating all sectors, pressures, and impacted components without requiring detailed information, though it benefits where this is available. Overall, it is an excellent first-level screening tool, identifying key risks and knowledge gaps.
Overall Weaknesses	No fine spatial or geospatial inputs and outputs are available. It requires expert groups and expert knowledge and is not directly compatible with policy. Robust assessments demand a large amount of diverse information, posing challenges in integrating varying data types, even within the same components (e.g., different measures of pressure) and considering the scale of assessment for different components. Another key weakness is the categorical nature of the inputs, preventing the ability to determine uncertainty statistically. The new approach developed in Aquacross has mitigated this. The outcomes are broad in scope, so fishing, for example, is usually considered a single sector but can be subdivided if needed.

Tool name	SCAIRM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (13, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional PACE management phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM18.2 - Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives <p>SCAIRM is able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements. The tool can be applied for all steps except Plan (of PACE), and its application is dependent on data availability.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>SCAIRM is able to assess all GES descriptors. The output is a measure of Impact Risk, which can be shown against GES Descriptors. Results could also</p>

Tool name	SCAIRM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	be linked to relevant criteria, but it does not assess if thresholds/targets are exceeded/reached.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCAIRM can be applied without quantitative input data. But if available, data can be used to assess exposure (spatial data of activities, pressures and ecosystem components) and/or the effect potential (dose-effect relations, specific recovery durations, etc). In all cases, quantitative data can be used to replace qualitative/semi-quantitative scores. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data).</p>

Tool name	SCAIRM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<p>Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>The SCAIRM tool can be applied using limited (qualitative or semi-quantitative) data, using spatial/temporal data (fully quantitative), or a combination of both. Scenarios can be evaluated, but the tool does not provide any trends as such.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The expertise required depends on the input data used. In the most basic application (qualitative/semi-quantitative), no specific expertise is required. If quantitative data is used, proficiency in GIS and/or R is necessary. Additionally, to analyse quantitative data on effects, some ecological knowledge is required.</p> <p>The tool runs on R code and associated databases, which are not yet publicly available.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<p>The tool runs on R code and associated databases, which are not yet publicly available.</p> <p>Links with GES4SEAS: Under GES4SEAS WP4, work is being undertaken on cumulative impact spatial mapping (with the development of the GES4SEAS toolbox), which will create linkages and synergies with the SCAIRM tool for impact risk ranking.</p>
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	No other potential barriers limiting the application of the tool.
Overall Strengths	It is a generic tool and not limited by data availability.
Overall Weaknesses	At this moment, it is mostly based on semi-quantitative data and without confidence assessment.

Tool name ODEMM (specific/particular tool)	
Tool group Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks	
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (10, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM 18.3 - Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. ODEMM is not standalone for most of the elements; it requires further development in terms of scale, resolution, and geospatial capabilities. While the tool is valuable for guiding assessments or providing a general overview of conditions, it lacks the necessary level of detail for conducting a comprehensive assessment; its primary role is in gross risk prioritisation. To maximize its effectiveness, it should integrate evidence and data from various sources. It is worth noting that more recent tool Aquacross was derived from ODEMM, and the principles underlying both tools can be adapted to suit a variety of purposes.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups

Tool name	ODEMM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>ODEMM is able to assess GES descriptors, mostly focusing on D1 (Biodiversity) and D6 (Seafloor integrity). One response indicated that the tool could be used for any descriptor, with the limiting factor being the evidence to support the weighting.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited in data-rich, skills-rich situations. In data-poor or skills-poor situations, it is considered moderately suited.</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Eco-components (not species groups) – as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity/Pressure footprint, eco-component distribution. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures, eco-components, interactions, effects and impacts. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components are required/produced.</p> <p>The tool deals with the assessment area as a point. Some spatial distributions might be considered within reasoning (knowledge), but they are not treated as input or output data. The same is true for temporal data,</p>

Tool name		ODEMM (specific/particular tool)	
Tool group		Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks	
		which is considered as one collective time in the assessment. Under the Defra UK-funded MSPri programme, a quantitative spatial and temporal aspect is being built.	
Confidence/Uncertainty		<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. The measure is qualitative, as experts put their level of confidence into the assessment.</p>	
Other resources required		<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Stakeholder engagement experience • Advanced knowledge on how to link multiple matrices if using a spreadsheet software, e.g., Excel <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (Spreadsheet software or R software).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>	
Tool references/links		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedreschi D., Bouch P., Moriarty M., Nixon E., Knights A. M., Reid D. G., 2019. Integrated ecosystem analysis in Irish waters; providing the context for ecosystem-based fisheries management. <i>Fisheries Research</i>, 209, 218–229. • Pedreschi D., Niiranen S., Skern-Mauritzen M., Reid D.G., 2023. Operationalising ODEMM risk assessment for Integrated Ecosystem Assessment scoping: Complexity vs. manageability. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i>, 9, 2766. 	
Strengths and Weaknesses			
Limitations to tool applicability		<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way. The general knowledge gaps in the impacts of human activities can be limiting. The tool assumes that all the users comprehend the categories and overlaps (severity, footprint, frequency, persistence, impact, recovery) and their local variability. Distribution of some pressures, particularly contaminants from land, can also be a limiting factor.</p>	
Barriers to tool application		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • The spreadsheet tables can be very large and take a long time to go through, with constant checking for consistency <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It should be applied within an expert group and with very clear guidelines. <p>One response reported that perhaps the biggest issue so far is that users have expected all the answers from a single tool. ODEMM and its variants</p>	

Tool name	ODEMM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	provide evidence to inspire future discussions, investigations, and evidence on trade-offs.
Overall Strengths	It is an expert-driven assessment of risk combinations. It is relatively easy to apply and can be used with numerous datasets of Activity, Pressure and Receptor linkages. When coupled with outputs such as Sankey plots, it can be very useful for inspiring discussions around what we really know about impacts on the environment.
Overall Weaknesses	Including a confidence factor is challenging; this aspect has not been well-addressed so far. Additionally, without knowledge about the effectiveness of management measures, it is difficult to incorporate them. This is a critical area that needs attention. The tool is not quantitative nor spatially differentiated (outputs). It only becomes temporal if repeated for a different time and compared. The overlap of pressures and components is not specific to a specific area. It is time and expert-intensive; it should ideally be conducted in a workshop setting. Pressures, activities, components and habitats need to be updated to align with the last MSFD definitions (2017), and interactions need to be re-evaluated.

Tool name Aquacross (specific/particular tool)	
Tool group Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks	
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Aquacross brings together evidence and data from numerous other sources to be most effective.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within other National Competent Authorities • Defra, UK (Marine Spatial Prioritisation (MSPri) Programme) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess any GES descriptor or criteria, with the limiting factor being the evidence to support the weighting.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).

Tool name	Aquacross (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial and temporal activities/pressures data and environmental receptors. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial and temporal activities/pressures data and environmental receptors. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial and temporal activities/pressures data and environmental receptors. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). No temporal components produced. Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year)

Tool name	Aquacross (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., >10 years) <p>Under the Defra UK-funded MSPri programme, a quantitative spatial and temporal aspect is being developed.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Stakeholder engagement experience <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool. However, it is more convenient to apply with R and GIS software, though not essential.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://aquacross.eu/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way. The general knowledge gaps in the impacts of human activities can be limiting. Distribution of some pressures, particularly things contaminants from land, can also be a limiting factor.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets
Overall Strengths	<p>It is relatively easy to apply and can be used with numerous datasets of Activity, Pressure and Receptor linkages. When coupled with outputs such as Sankey plots, it can be very useful for inspiring discussions around what we really know about impacts on the environment.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>Including a confidence factor is challenging; this aspect has not been well-addressed so far. Additionally, without knowledge about the effectiveness of management measures, it is difficult to incorporate them.</p>

Tool name	ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (17, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. ICES/Mission Atlantic variation is highly valuable as an initial screening tool, providing a comprehensive perspective and helping to prioritise and narrow the scope further. Like all Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks tools, it informs on context, risk, priorities and gaps. However, for quantitative assessments, supplementary tools are needed.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making • The tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development

Tool name	ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess all GES descriptors and criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated (usually by informing a scale, risk, impact or condition score). Maps and temporal data (occurrence, frequency, effort) are the most useful. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All the input variables are included in a semi-quantitative way. Nothing specific is required, but all available data relating to components can be used. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components are required/produced.</p> <p>All information can be incorporated (including spatial and temporal data) and used to inform risk scores. However, the bare minimum is expert and/or stakeholder knowledge.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological knowledge • Knowledge of social, economic and governance systems • Familiarity with the approach and experience with running workshops, stakeholder engagement and facilitating such exercises <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scripts for analysis are available at https://github.com/missionatlantic/MissionAtlantic-RISK-Analysis

Tool name	ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1037878
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. It assumes directionality of effects and does not account for interactions among pressures/sectors.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires focus groups to be applied • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acceptable risk levels could be identified - but this is likely a case by case/regional issue. • If used as a part of a wider assessment, and treated as a living document, the risk assessment is easier to maintain and remains useful. This also limits the need for additional focus groups. Many regions already have an assessment that can be adapted/built on.
Overall Strengths	The tool is relatively simple, and (once learnt) is easily updated. It allows a holistic view of all relevant aspects and can be carried out in data-rich and poor situations. It is an excellent first step for many analyses - enabling prioritising and focusing effort on more quantitative analyses while identifying knowledge gaps.
Overall Weaknesses	It does not take interactions into account (cumulative and or interactive effects). Current scoring categories are broad, limiting detailed inferences (improvements in progress).

Single species models

Single-species models are mathematical representations used to study and understand the dynamics of a particular species within an ecosystem. The models focus on the population size, growth, and interactions of a single species, while often considering the species' interactions with its environment and other factors that influence its population dynamics. These models can incorporate limited ecosystem or multispecies information. Single-species models are useful for understanding factors influencing the abundance, distribution, and sustainability of marine organisms by, for example, elucidating causal processes underpinning declines of individual species. Single-species models have also been traditionally used in fisheries management for estimating stock status and fluctuations over time and providing management advice (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Single species models (generic tool, #8) [2 responses, Familiar].

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*1.3) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*0.9) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*0.6) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.6) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.4) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*0.9) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*0.5) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*1) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*3.3) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.4) • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.7)

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*1.3) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*1.9) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*2.1) • EBM17 – Risks (*1.7) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*1.6) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. While single species models are the best approach for managing fish stocks, true EBM needs a combination with ecosystem models such as EwE or Atlantis, among others. This is because the approach primarily provides information on biomass and fishing mortality for the assessed species, typically commercial stocks. Therefore, it does not encompass the entirety of ecosystem components but is an essential part of Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management (EBFM). To extend beyond the fishing activity-pressure-state links, it is necessary to incorporate other functional relationships, such as the impact of climate change on recruitment. Without these additions, the tool remains primarily focused on fisheries-related aspects. Although it could potentially be expanded to include direct links with climate change and primary production, it still operates at the single species level.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the achievement of overarching policy goals, in particular in the Common Fisheries Policy and as elements of the MSFD D3 assessment for criteria D3C1 and D3C2
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish); D3C1; D3C2 D1 (Biodiversity)
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in situations of data-poor or skills-poor situations and poorly suited in data-poor, skills-poor situations.</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities - as multiple variables Pressures - as multiple variables Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities - as multiple variables Pressures - as multiple variables Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landings and catches (by metier, season), fishery-independent data (abundance, biomass, size, maturity), biological data (growth, asymptotic length, etc.). <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the absence of catches, survey indices can be used. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> None. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p>

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. Depending on the application, in theory, the variance of all inputs is considered, but rarely taken full advantage of, e.g., surveys.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. Depending on the application, but most models can provide error bounds for both the current estimates and projections under different fishing scenarios.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (e.g., SAMtool: Stock Assessment Methods Toolkit).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SAMtool: Stock Assessment Methods Toolkit - https://rdr.io/cran/SAMtool/man/SAMtool-package.html
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way. The most relevant assumptions are about life history parameters being consistent, and also assumptions about stock-recruitment relationships and their consistency and not being affected by ecosystem variables, such as temperature.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • Depending on the data available, approaches may differ (the lower the data quality, the higher the uncertainty in the output) <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single-stock assessments are accessible for numerous species, yet commercial species of minor interest receive limited consideration or assessment. To address the constraint of data availability, one option is to increase the provision of sampling data through enhanced catch monitoring and more accurate surveys. Another option is to facilitate the testing or official adoption of methods for reporting poor data that could improve the spread of assessments.
Overall Strengths	<p>The tool is applicable in data-rich and data-poor conditions and provides uncertainty. It can allow tracking of several species and a good share of ecosystem components. Clear pressure-state relationship underpinning it. It can be used directly to provide management thresholds and targets and to assess the effectiveness of measures. It is broadly understood conceptually by stakeholders.</p>

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
Overall Weaknesses	It is a single-species tool, so multispecies and ecosystem interactions are not accounted for. Most often, environmental drivers are not considered (although they could be included in assessments, e.g., primary production). There are too many assumptions when applying the tool, such as stock-recruitment relationships, steady state in growth, maturity, etc. Increasing complexity in specific models often results in a decrease in understanding from stakeholders.

Biogeochemical models

Biogeochemical models capture two-way interactions between the biology and chemistry of ecosystems. They are used to simulate how abiotic and biotic variables interact through time and across space and provide a means to explore management scenarios in relation to climate change and changes in the flow of nutrients from land into the ocean. Typically, biogeochemical models are used to study nutrient cycling (nitrogen, phosphorus, oxygen, silicon, and iron) and impacts on planktonic communities due to events such as eutrophication and oxygen depletion (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Biogeochemical models (generic tool, #9) [1 response, Expert].
- DCPM box model, also biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR (specific/particular tool, #9.1) [1 response, Familiar].

Tool name		Biogeochemical models (generic tool)
Tool group		Biogeochemical models
Uses of the tool		
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*0.7) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*1.3) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*1) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*0.7) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*1.3) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*1.3) • EBM13 - Climate change (*2) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*1) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*0.7) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.5) 	

Tool name	Biogeochemical models (generic tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM17 – Risks (*0.5) <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act <p>Biogeochemical models are able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria, mostly D5 (Eutrophication) and related criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in situations of data-poor or skills-poor situations and poorly suited in data-poor, skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tides, meteo, nutrients. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>The model is differential equation-based and deals with quantitative inputs/outputs only. Qualitative products would require human interpretation.</p> <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data).</p> <p>Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps).</p>

Tool name	
Biogeochemical models (generic tool)	
Tool group	
Biogeochemical models	
	<p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting).</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Modelling • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>Additional resources needed include access to high-performance computers for large-scale 3D computation.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.pml.ac.uk/science/projects/ERSEM-(European-Regional-Seas-Ecosystem-Model). • Savchuk O.P., Gustafsson B.G., Muller-Karulis B., 2012. BALTSEM – a marine model for decision support within the Baltic Sea Region. Technical Report No 7. Baltic Nest Institute. Stockholm. • Butenschon M., Clark J., Aldridge J.N., Allen J.I., Artioli Y., Blackford J., Bruggeman J., Cazenave P., Ciavatta S., Kay S., Lessin G., van Leeuwen S., van der Molen J., de Mora L., Polimene L., Sailley S., Stephens N., Torres R., 2016. ERSEM 15.06: a generic model for marine biogeochemistry and the ecosystem dynamics of the lower trophic levels. <i>Geoscientific Model Development</i>, 9(4), 1293–1339.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, mostly because the models generally are not species-specific and are limited to the lower trophic levels.
Barriers to tool application	No potential barriers to tool application.
Overall Strengths	Within its domain of biogeochemistry and lower trophic levels (LTL), it encompasses numerous interactions and feedbacks. It can be applied to a wide range of scenarios, including climate, nutrient reduction, and trawling impacts.
Overall Weaknesses	Results depend on a large number of often poorly constrained parameters. Structural uncertainty arises from our (incomplete) knowledge of

Tool name	Biogeochemical models (generic tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
	biogeochemical interactions, requiring some (possibly) simplistic assumptions.

Tool name	DCPM box model and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (12, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM13 - Climate change <p>DCPM box model and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR have the potential to fully deliver against the above EBM elements. While they primarily focus on eutrophication, they can readily be coupled with other tools to consider climate change, pelagic habitats, food webs and more.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria, mostly D5 (Eutrophication) and related criteria (e.g., D5C1, D5C2).
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations.

Tool name	DCPM box model and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Riverine flows, nutrients, chl <i>a</i>, opportunistic algae, catchment size or area for larger models, salinity gradients, residence time. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data); No temporal components produced. Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Ecological knowledge
Tool references/links	No references or links provided.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data
Overall Strengths	Strengths include the development of thresholds across an entire region rather than nationally developed thresholds. It allows the identification of further monitoring requirements and the use of satellite chlorophyll <i>a</i> data

Tool name	DCPM box model and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
	as an input. The tool also has the potential for considering climate change impacts and their possible effect on future threshold values.
Overall Weaknesses	Weaknesses include discrepancies in results when employing different models and the challenge of identifying ways to reconcile these differences.

Food-web models

Food-web (or mass-balance) models are a particular type of ecosystem models, which are often visualised as networks, where nodes denote interacting ecological components, and the causal relationships between them are shown by edges. They simulate the structure and flow of energy and nutrients between ecosystem components and are commonly used for quantifying food web interactions in a whole-ecosystem context. Generally, for modelling, multiple species are aggregated according to a certain criterion and represent a single species, groups of species or ontogenic phases of a species (juveniles and adults), which are different compartments in the network. Food web models aim to understand the population dynamics among predators and prey, the stability of communities and the implications of change for ecosystem structure, functioning and stability, as well as the flow of matter/energy among the nodes as an ecosystem or ecological network (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool, #10.1) [3 responses; 1 Very familiar, 2 Familiar].

Tool name		Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group		Food-web models
Uses of the tool		
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation 	

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18.1 - Other policy requirements - MSPD • EBM18.2 - Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives • EBM 18.3 - Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>EwE and Ecospace have the potential to fully address the EBM elements mentioned above. However, their usefulness depends on the specific configurations of individual models and the inclusion or highlighting of particular groups and functions. For instance, when dealing with Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) and Non-Indigenous Species (NIS), their incorporation as part of groups or individual species significantly influences the utility of the results for the purposes mentioned. This consideration also applies to birds. Moreover, for single species or single function assessments, there are more specialised tools available, although EwE can certainly be employed in such cases as well.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1 (Biodiversity); D1C1; D1C2; D1C4 • D2 (Non-indigenous species); D2C1; D2C2 • D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish); D3C1; D3C2 • D4 (Food webs); D4C1, D4C2; D4C4 • D8C1
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. The suitability decreases with decreasing amounts of data and poor skills, becoming not suitable in data-poor, skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variables depend on the question addressed. Ecopath needs species diet matrices and abundance of the initial year. Ecosim requires a time-series of any variable: oceanographic, fishing effort, mortality, abundances, etc. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecospace maps can be semi-quantitative. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecospace maps can be qualitative. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting).</p>

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
	<p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>EwE explicitly uses time series as inputs, such as catch rates, biomass of components, etc. It can then output modelled trends. As Ecospace, it can use spatial distribution data from known features (e.g., fishing effort) and output spatially resolved species abundances, etc. All of these depend on the model and how it is built. However, Ecospace allows spatial-temporal input layers and produces spatial-temporal data. Spatial and temporal inputs are not required for the tool to work—again, this depends on the model and how it is built.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. All uncertainties associated with input parameters can be addressed. These measures can then be used to assess the uncertainty of the results. It is a qualitative assessment.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. EwE produces confidence intervals if the input data uncertainty is addressed in Ecopath.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>Additional resources needed include access to MS Access to work with EwE.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colleter M., Valls A., Guitton J., Gascuel D., Pauly D., Christensen V., 2015. Global overview of the applications of the Ecopath with Ecosim modeling approach using the EcoBase models repository. Ecological Modelling 302: 42-53 • https://ecopath.org/ <p>Links with GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under Task 3.4, capacity-building activities for Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace are being organised.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>While most responses (67%) considered that the tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable, the remaining reported that the tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. These assumptions relate to diet makeup, primary productivity, and mechanistic links.</p>

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring time series, oceanography, species abundances, fishing effort, and other human stressors are essential. Although it requires some initial data to start constructing the diet matrix, estimates can be made. • Initially, EwE may seem overwhelming, so connecting with an experienced user is often advisable.
Overall Strengths	<p>It is a quantitative approach that gives a complete ecosystem perspective. The tool itself has wide capabilities. It is relatively simple to use. It can be adapted to many different situations and questions. It started life as a fisheries tool, but has been applied to contaminants, HABs, etc. It can be used to evaluate lots of scenarios, especially in Ecosim. It can be used to work with stakeholders.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>It might be too easy to use. The mass balancing in Ecopath presents numerous potential outcomes, as it is only necessary to balance the energy flows without needing to be extremely precise. However, this approach could lead to unrealistic solutions, and therefore, the tool should be used with the guidance of an expert user. The functional group approach used can be arbitrary, so species can be grouped together by size, shape, or any other characteristic. It does not work well with more than 30+ functional groups. Each region/location needs to have a model built using the local data. The model building takes a lot of time and resources and hence limits the usability.</p>

Ecosystem models

Ecosystem models describe the interactions between at least two ecosystem components (e.g., populations, species, functional groups), whereby the interactions are real ecological processes (e.g., predator–prey interactions, large and small perturbations, dispersal). End-to-end (E2E) models, a specific type of ecosystem model, offer a comprehensive mathematical representation of an entire ecosystem. They integrate physicochemical oceanographic factors with organisms ranging from microbes to higher-trophic-level organisms, including humans, and connect to marine socio-economic aspects. Developed for Ecosystem-Based Management, E2E models address bottom-up and top-down controls that operate simultaneously and vary in time and space, accommodating multiple impacts. These models are employed to characterise the current ecosystem, project scenarios, and inform management decisions (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023). Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Ecosystem models (generic tool, #11) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Ecosystem models (generic tool)
Tool group	Ecosystem models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.3) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*2) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*3.5) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*2.1) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.5) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*3.3) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1.1) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*2.4) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.4) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.4) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.4) • EBM13 - Climate change (*2.3)

Tool name	Ecosystem models (generic tool)
Tool group	Ecosystem models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*2) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.7) • EBM17 – Risks (*1.8) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM18.1 - Other policy requirements - MSPD <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check <p>The tool is able to fully deliver against the selected EBM elements. It is best suited for 'what-if' planning scenarios, but it can also serve as a counterfactual tool to understand effects or for conducting benefit evaluations. There is potential to use it in planning monitoring activities, although it is advisable not to rely on it for annual decision-making processes. Additionally, it can be employed to characterise impact response functions, which can then be integrated into other tools (e.g., the Halpern modified Halpern approach) for the analysis of non-additive effects.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess all GES descriptors and criteria.</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. Skills are highly relevant for using this tool, making it moderately suited for data-poor situations and poorly or even not suitable for skills-poor situations.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables

Tool name	Ecosystem models (generic tool)
Tool group	Ecosystem models
	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numbers or biomass of each biological component of the model (typically biomass pools for invertebrates and abundance at age for vertebrates) - which might be species or functional group of taxonomic resolution. In addition, it needs a map of the bottom type and time series of hydrodynamic flows and physical environmental state (temperature, salinity, etc.). <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While the quantitative values input might be "best guess" and thus, in theory, semi-quantitative, all inputs are treated as quantitative. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps).</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting).</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., >10 years) <p>The tool requires spatial initial conditions and time series of forcing for activities if they are not dynamically represented within the model. It also needs parameters defining the timing of processes such as migration and reproduction. The output is a 3D spatially resolved time-series for each model variable.</p>
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p>

Tool name	Ecosystem models (generic tool)
Tool group	Ecosystem models
	<p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. It is necessary to run multiple simulations with different parameterisations across plausible parameter spaces to produce confidence bands. The model will not do that in isolation (i.e., the user has to do the runs; the model does not just produce confidence bands on the output), but it is best practice.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (e.g., Atlantis).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://research.csiro.au/atlantis/home/links/ • www.mathstat.strath.ac.uk/outreach/e2e
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. The user must define what options are being used for movement, recruitment, feeding relationships, etc. Once selected, the model will use the assumptions inherent in those relationships. The model also makes some simple assumptions about how things are distributed (homogeneous, Poisson, etc.) within a spatial cell.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<p>Suggestions to overcome barriers to tool application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert user guidance/training can help any new users deal with data shortages/patchiness and how to follow best practice guidelines in model use
Overall Strengths	<p>It represents the dynamic spatiotemporal outcomes of the complexity of interactions and processes that occur in real systems. This extends beyond equilibrium assumptions, static maps and the assumption of additive in cumulative effects.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>Data-intensive can be hard to use (e.g., Atlantis) or easily accidentally misused (e.g., Ecopath with Ecosim*), so it is best to have an expert user to guide any new users.</p> <p><i>*Note: Ecopath with Ecosim is a food-web model – a specific case of Ecosystem Models. For details on this tool refer to the tool group “Food-web models”.</i></p>

Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)

Habitat suitability models (HSM), also referred to in the literature as species distribution models (SDMs) or predictive habitat distribution models, are predictive models used to predict the spatial distribution of species based on their observed relationship with environmental conditions. On calibration of the model, the species-environment relationship is established based on data on the species distribution and the environmental conditions where it occurs. It is used to identify the key environmental predictors which determine the suitability of a location for the species. On prediction, the environmental conditions are used as predictors of the likelihood of the presence or density of the species throughout a study area. As such, this modelling approach can be seen as an operational application of the potential ecological niche (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool, #12) [2 responses; 1 Expert, 1 Very familiar].

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (11, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.5) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*1.9) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.8) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*3.2) • EBM13 - Climate change (*2.4) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*2.1) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.9) • EBM17 – Risks (*1.8) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
	<p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Species distribution models (SDMs) are able to fully deliver against the selected EBM elements. The tool enables the assessment and prediction of the environmental envelope of marine species, thus predicting the distribution of these biodiversity assets, including potential changes, such as those resulting from different climate scenarios. Consequently, SDMs play a crucial role in supporting planning efforts by identifying areas of risk, where negative interactions between assets and activities may occur, and by pinpointing conservation priority areas. These priority areas can be determined, for instance, by combining the results of SDMs for multiple species, aiding in the designation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and highlighting diversity hotspots.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • Research supporting management (a fisheries management tool in the US (through Essential Fish Habitats), trying to be implemented in the UK) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool can assess GES descriptors and criteria. While it does not provide a direct assessment, the outputs of SDMs support assessments primarily related to D1 (Biodiversity). Examples of criteria include D1C2, D1C4, D1C5, and D2C2.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-rich, skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for any data-poor situation.</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p>

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species distribution and abundance data (density, catches, sightings, etc.) - from monitoring. Environmental data layers (oceanographic, topographic, geomorphologic, etc., variables) to calibrate and predict the model. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maybe species abundance could be represented in a semiquantitative way (e.g., on a discrete scale/score), but it's unusual. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species occurrence (presence/absence) from monitoring, if no abundance data are available. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p> <p>Spatial inputs = spatial layers of environmental data (model predictors) + spatial distribution of monitoring data (abundances, sightings, etc.). Spatial outputs = maps of predicted species variable (e.g., probability of presence, density). Temporal inputs = not really a requirement, but the wider spatial and temporal coverage of the input data (e.g., for multiple years), the better the model predictions are likely to be (higher confidence). A SDM does not per se provide future trends, as its outputs represent a snapshot in time (related to the timing of the environmental predictor layers to which the model is applied). However, if environmental layers are available as predictions for multiple points in future time, the different outputs from the SDM application to each of these can be interpreted to forecast potential future trends in the species distribution.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The confidence can be estimated qualitatively based on the quality of the input data. Quantitative estimates (S.D., CV) can also be used. The tool allows, for instance, the inclusion of information about sampling bias as input data.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS, such as statistical confidence based on model predictive ability. Additional</p>

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
	confidence estimates can be combined with statistical confidence based on the quality of the input data, their uncertainty, etc. The tool can also produce uncertainty maps in addition to the maps about the potential distribution of species/habitats.
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs. The models can be implemented using various statistical approaches (GLM, GAMS, CART, etc.), and R software can be used for this purpose. However, there may be some statistical packages that offer specific applications.</p> <p>Additional resources needed depend on the volume of data - a computational cluster may be required to model large datasets.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fortuna, C.M., Cañadas, A., Holcer, D., Brecciaroli, B., Donovan, G.P., Lazar, B., Mo, G., Tunesi, L. and Mackelworth, P.C., 2018. The coherence of the European Union marine Natura 2000 network for wide-ranging charismatic species: a Mediterranean case study. <i>Frontiers In Marine Science</i>, 5, p.356. • Sillero, N., Arenas-Castro, S., Enriquez-Urzelai, U., Vale, C.G., Sousa-Guedes, D., Martínez-Freiría, F., Real, R. and Barbosa, A.M., 2021. Want to model a species niche? A step-by-step guideline on correlative ecological niche modelling. <i>Ecological Modelling</i>, 456, p.109671 • Naimi, B. and Araújo, M.B., 2016. sdm: a reproducible and extensible R platform for species distribution modelling. <i>Ecography</i>, 39(4), pp.368-375. • Galparsoro, I., Á. Borja, J. Bald, P. Liria, G. Chust, 2009. Predicting suitable habitat for the European lobster (<i>Homarus gammarus</i>), on the Basque continental shelf (Bay of Biscay), using Ecological-Niche Factor Analysis. <i>Ecological Modelling</i>, 220: 556-567 https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0304380008005395 • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=83dMS3bcjJM
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. One such assumption is that observed species-environment relationships can be extrapolated for prediction. While the tool can be theoretically applied anywhere, users must consider the validity and confidence in predictions, especially beyond calibrated environmental ranges, for appropriate use and interpretation of the outputs. The tool benefits from the availability of wide-ranging and long-term datasets, resulting in better confidence and wider validity of results. Additionally, the tool assumes that the species assessed is in equilibrium with the environment, the biases in the modelling system are minimal, all predictors included in the model describe the species niche, and that the species niche is conserved across space and time.

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available <p>The tool can be applied with limited data, but this would affect the confidence and validity of outputs. Data from broad-scale sampling programmes is preferred to provide input data on species. Limited availability of species monitoring data and of environmental data layers (for model calibration and prediction) in certain areas (e.g., inshore/estuarine areas) may be a barrier to the model implementation.</p> <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement broad-scale, coordinated/harmonised monitoring programmes (species and environmental variables) encompassing poorly covered areas.
Overall Strengths	<p>The tool allows mapping potential distribution of biodiversity assets (species) in an objective way (based on an environmental envelope), thus supporting the identification of key areas for spatial management (conservation, MPAs, areas of risk). It provides continuous estimations of species/habitat's potential distribution over the study area using point information on species occurrence/abundance. Some specific techniques were developed to overcome limitations related to data-poor species.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>The models are data-driven, so the quality of the data is key to the quality of the output (affecting confidence). One model applies to one species (but outputs can be combined across species in a community, e.g., to identify biodiversity hotspots). A continuous representation of the environmental predictors over the study area is required in order to produce maps of potential distribution for species/habitats. This requirement is sometimes difficult to achieve for all ecologically relevant predictors, particularly for future environmental conditions when the objective is to forecast the impacts of climate change on the species/habitats distribution range.</p>

Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation

The natural capital approach to policy and decision-making considers the value of the natural environment for people and the economy, providing a tool to support the protection and management of the natural environment and to facilitate the engagement of stakeholders within management decisions. Natural capital accounts are developed to assess and monitor the contribution of natural resources to economic activity. Physical accounts tables provide basic information on the state of the environment (the stock and the flows of the natural capital, analogous to ecological structure and functioning) in a specific geographical area. When a condition table is also populated, this information can indicate at what level of the ecosystem an impact of economic activities is occurring (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool, #13) [2 responses; 1 Very familiar, 1 Familiar].
- Ocean Accounts (specific/particular tool, #13.1) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (11, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*0.8) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*4.7) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*2.7) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABS) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*0.5) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*1) • EBM13 - Climate change (*0.8) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*1.8) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy

Tool name	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
	<p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. The tool focusses on natural capital and ecosystem service valuation and not all aspects of the ecosystem. Its foundation lies in monetary valuation, and currently, not all benefits derived from ecosystem services can be quantified in monetary terms. Furthermore, the tool is not yet fully developed or operationalized. Non-monetary valuation is an area that is currently receiving significant attention in research.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • National governments (national reporting) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-rich, skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for any data-poor situation.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as single variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as single variables

Tool name	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat extent, geography and condition, and prices of societal benefits secured from ecosystem services. Where possible, both spatial and temporal data to provide the best outputs. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation. <p>Qualitative components are an additional source of information to supplement the monetary values derived from these tools.</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. EUNIS habitats have associated confidence scores. There are assumptions made regarding confidence in monetary prices inputted into the tools.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge

Tool name	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economics • Management <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is readily available, but there are associated purchase and/or licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gacutan, J., Pınarbaşı K., Agbaglah M., Bradley C., Galparsoro I., Murillas A., Adewumi I., Praphotjanaporn T., Bordt M., Findlay K., Lantz C., Milligan B. M., 2022a. The emerging intersection between marine spatial planning and ocean accounting: A global review and case studies. <i>Marine Policy</i>, 140: 105055. The model described in this paper is operational and freely available here: https://aztidata.es/vapem/ • United Nations et al. (2021). System of Environmental-Economic Accounting— Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA). White cover publication, pre-edited text subject to official editing. Available at: https://seea.un.org/ecosystem-accounting. <p>Links with GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under Task 3.4, capacity-building activities for Capacity to Deliver Ecosystem Services and links to GES are being organised.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, primarily influenced by the confidence in valuation and mapping data, often focusing on one biological element at a time in some cases.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements • It requires focus groups to be applied • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • It requires the availability of habitat and valuation data <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More evidence collection on societal benefits and their value. Identification of data gaps within EUNIS mapping. • Time and resources.
Overall Strengths	Strengths include ensuring the societal benefits of natural environments are included within wider accounting and inform decision-making. There are standard sets of agreed rules (e.g., UN SEEA) emerging for the application of these tools, and this facilitates consistent application across geographical locations and over time.
Overall Weaknesses	Data availability impacting on its ability to cover societal benefits in a comprehensive way. The tool is still in development.

Tool name Ocean Accounts (specific/particular tool)	
Tool group Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation	
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (9, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Ocean accounts require environmental/ecosystem services valuation tools, as they are separate from accounting. The tool is useful to provide information to decision support systems.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • The Global Ocean Accounts Partnership (GOAP) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors and criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor, skills-poor situations.

Tool name	Ocean Accounts (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as single variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses or management measures - as single variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat extent, geography and condition, and prices of societal benefits secured from ecosystem services. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. This is a recent functionality of the tool.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. This is a recent functionality of the tool.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Economics <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs, but its application to the marine environment is still in development (ARIES).</p>

Tool name	Ocean Accounts (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
	No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://aries.integratedmodelling.org/ (the application to the marine environment is still in development)
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, depending on the ecosystem service considered.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collecting more ad hoc data
Overall Strengths	The tool provides a complete, succinct summary of the environmental extent, condition and economic value of an area.
Overall Weaknesses	It is still a recent tool and is under experimentation/development.

Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation

This tool group includes tools such as: (i) Bio-economic models, i.e. integrated economic-ecological models used for resource management and sustainable resource use; (ii) Valuation of Societal Benefits, which determines the ‘total social value’ (comprising of ecological value, economic value, and socio-cultural value) of marine ecosystem services leading to benefits for society; (iii) Cost-benefit analysis (CBA), a core tool of public policy consisting in the systematic process of calculating the benefits and costs, expressed in monetary units, of policy options and projects (environmental CBA is the application of CBA to projects or policies that have the deliberate aim of environmental improvement or actions that somehow affect the natural environment as an indirect consequence) (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool, #14) [1 response, Very familiar].

Tool name	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (5, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*5) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change (*0.5) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*1.5) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives <p>In its current state, the tool is able to address PACE management phases, but the respondent was unsure when.</p> <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements, as these tools focus on monetary valuation.</p>

Tool name	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • National governments <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor and skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat extent, geography and condition, and prices of societal benefits secured from ecosystem services. Where possible, both spatial and temporal data to provide the best outputs. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation. <p>Qualitative components are an additional source of information to supplement the monetary values derived from these tools.</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km)

Tool name	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., >10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Economics <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is readily available, but there are associated purchase and/or licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atkins J.P., Burdon D., Elliott M., Gregory A.J., 2011. Management of the marine environment: integrating ecosystem services and societal benefits with the DPSIR framework in a systems approach. <i>Marine Pollution Bulletin</i>, 62, pp. 215-226 • Burdon D., Boyes S.J., Elliott M., Smyth K., Atkin J.P., Barnes R.A., Wurzel R.K., 2018. Integrating natural and social marine science to sustainably manage vectors of change: Dogger Bank transnational case study. <i>Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science</i> 201: 234-247
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, primarily influenced by the confidence in valuation and mapping data.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements • It requires focus groups to be applied • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • It requires the availability of habitat and valuation data <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More evidence collection on societal benefits and their value • Time and resources

Tool name	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation
Overall Strengths	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation tools measure the benefits of the natural environment to human welfare in value terms and thereby support decision-making.
Overall Weaknesses	These tools attempt to provide evidence to inform decision-making on aspects which have not previously been included in decision-making as such evidence was absent.

Spatial planning models and tools

Spatial planning models, adapted to the marine environment, are tools used to help planners and policymakers make informed decisions about the use of marine space and resources. The models are designed to provide insights into the potential impacts of different planning scenarios, and to help identify the most effective strategies for achieving specific planning goals. There are several different types of spatial planning models, each of which is suited to different types of planning challenges. Overall, these models play a crucial role in supporting informed decision-making by evaluating the impact of diverse land-use and development scenarios on environmental quality and natural resources. They contribute to the identification of vulnerable areas, habitat loss, or other environmental hazards, and evaluate the effectiveness of different conservation strategies (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool, #15) [1 response, Very familiar].
- GIS – Geographic Information System (specific/particular tool, #15.1) [1 response, Very familiar].

Tool name		Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool)
Tool group		Spatial planning models and tools
Uses of the tool		
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (10, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.8) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*1.5) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*1.7) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.2) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*2.9) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*2.5) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*1.5) • EBM17 – Risks (*2.1) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.5) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy 	

Tool name		Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool)	
Tool group		Spatial planning models and tools	
		<p>D2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023) identified the tool to deliver the following EBM elements (with score > 4, as per Table 27 of 2.1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Check • Evaluate <p>The tool is able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements.</p>	
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management		<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • For EEA assessments • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making • Design of remediation/management measures • Development of MSFD thresholds 	
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed		The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.	
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs			
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation		The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in any other situation.	
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool		<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as single variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables 	

Tool name	
Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool)	
Tool group	
Spatial planning models and tools	
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution of activities and pressures, and potentially their intensity. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables can be semi-quantitative data. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables can be qualitative data. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (QGIS).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • www.qgis.org • VAPEM tool: Environmental Assessment and Marine Spatial Planning tool: https://aztidata.es/vapem/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. These assumptions could involve factors such as the knowledge on the spatial distribution of some variables. Despite these assumptions, mapping can still be performed; however, the accuracy may be reduced compared to using more detailed data.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets

Tool name	Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
Overall Strengths	The spatial aspect is the strength, as this allows for analyses that are not restricted to a single spot.
Overall Weaknesses	It requires good knowledge of the tool and how to properly handle the data.

Tool name	
GIS – Geographic Information System (specific/particular tool)	
Tool group	
Spatial planning models and tools	
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (13, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. For example, the tool does not have any associated thresholds or targets to determine GES.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and Criteria. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1C2; D1C4; D1C5; D1C6 • D2C1; D2C3 • D5C3 D5C8 • D6 (Sea-floor integrity) • D7 (Hydrographical changes) • D8C3

Tool name	GIS – Geographic Information System (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D10C1; D10C2
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor and skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures, species abundance, species potential distribution, area/extent. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures, risk. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities, habitat, species occurrence. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data); Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., >10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>

Tool name	GIS – Geographic Information System (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • GIS <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (e.g., QGIS).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://qgis.org/en/docs/index.html
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets
Overall Strengths	GIS allows storing, managing and mapping different types of data (e.g., physical, biological, environmental, ecological, geological, etc) that can be further analysed using spatial analysis supported by statistical and modelling approaches. These capabilities can, therefore, support monitoring of, for instance, detrimental environmental changes and shifts in species distribution and habitat extent and, at the same time, support the development of mitigation/restoration measures.
Overall Weaknesses	It requires expertise in manipulating and processing spatial data and georeferenced information.

Conservation planning models

Conservation planning is the process of locating, configuring, implementing and maintaining areas that are managed to promote the persistence of biodiversity and other natural values. Systematic conservation planning (SCP) uses an explicit and transparent methodology to locate and design new reserves complementing the existing network of protected areas. It applies explicit criteria for implementing conservation actions and adopting explicit objectives and mechanisms for maintaining the needed conditions in protected areas required to foster the persistence of the protected ecological features (used as surrogates for overall biodiversity), as well as adequate monitoring schemes and adaptive management. SCP is goal-oriented (with operational targets) and recognizes the level of achievement of conservation goals in the existing protected areas. Decision support tools have been developed to facilitate systematic conservation planning, the most widely used being MARXAN and ZONATION (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023). Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool, #16) [1 response, Very familiar].
- MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool, #16.1) [2 responses, Very familiar].

Tool name	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (11, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*1.8) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*0.8) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*2.2) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.7) • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.6) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.3) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*4.6) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*2) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*3.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy

Tool name	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. For some EBM elements, outputs from additional tools are needed, such as Species Distribution Models, Cumulative Impact Mapping, GIS, and vulnerability assessments (linking activities, pressures, and impacts).</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited in any skills-rich situations and poorly suited in any skills-poor situations.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p>

Tool name	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species abundance, habitat coverage, metrics of activities/pressures (e.g., actual fishing effort per grid cell, level of disturbance by towed gears), and contribution of human activities to GDP. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indices of species abundance, indices of the intensity of human activities. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For species, habitats, and activities: presence data or data in a Likert scale (e.g., low/medium/high abundance - low/medium/high fishing effort). <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., >100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. For instance, Marxan with Probability considers 4 types of uncertainty: the probability that a feature exists in a particular place; the probability that features in a site will be lost in the future due to a threatening process; the probability that a feature will exist in the future due to natural successional processes; and probability the feature exists but has been degraded by threatening processes, such as overfishing or pollution, and thus cannot contribute to conservation goals.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. Multiple runs are necessary to produce selection frequency maps (indicating how often, under different runs, a grid cell is proposed to be prioritised for protection). High frequencies indicate high confidence in the importance of specific cells.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Knowledge of the use of specific software (e.g., MARXAN, ZONATION, prioritizer)

Tool name	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://marxansolutions.org/ • https://zonationteam.github.io/Zonation5/ • https://prioritizr.net/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. For example, specific assumptions about connectivity regarding ecosystem components or threats, data-driven assumptions about the distribution of ecological components, and assumptions about the vulnerability of ecological components to specific activities/pressures.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It requires focus groups to be applied <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species distribution models (SDMs) can be used to deal with data gaps. • Adaptive management.
Overall Strengths	<p>The tool provides an efficient and cost-effective way of creating/expanding MPA networks, e.g., to support the Biodiversity Strategy, accounting for both the distribution of ecological and socioeconomic features as well as accounting for existing spatial management measures.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>It is not easy for the stakeholders to perceive how the outputs of the tool have been produced. Although the tool is based on a transparent methodology, high technical and analytical skills are required for its implementation.</p>

Tool name	MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM17 - Risks <p>MARXAN family tools are able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements. The tool has the capacity to integrate a wide range of information and outputs from other tools, depending on the concept developed and the questions set.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development

Tool name	MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations and poorly suited in any skills-poor situations. In data-poor, skills-rich situations, the tool is moderately suited.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The full distribution of features (e.g., species, habitat, process, cultural site, etc.) targeted for protection expressed as continuous values (e.g., species population, model outputs, indicators, proxies); pressures and management cost expressed in relevant units (e.g., fishing effort) or as distance-based cost; opportunity cost or action-based cost; numerical conservation targets for each feature targeted for protection, etc. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution of features (e.g., species, habitat, process, cultural site, etc.) targeted for protection based on expert judgement; or through indicators and proxies; presence of an activity (e.g., port); cost expressed as pressure (e.g., fishing effort) or as distance/area-based cost. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km)

Tool name	MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p> <p>As outputs represent a snapshot in time, to obtain temporal outputs, it is possible to run the tool multiple times using relevant information that corresponds to the targeted temporal scale (e.g., per season).</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The tool provides output showing the number of times each planning unit was selected across all solutions (selection frequency). It provides an indication of how useful each planning unit is for creating an efficient reserve system. See also Confidence/Uncertainty information for the generic tool.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. It allows the development of portfolios of solutions.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://marxansolutions.org/software/ • https://prioritizr.net/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires focus groups to be applied • No temporal or 3-d dimension • In some cases, proxies for socio-economic data may have high uncertainty <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the temporal dimension, it is possible to run MARXAN multiple times using the relevant information that corresponds to the targeted temporal scale (e.g., per season).
Overall Strengths	MARXAN is the most widely used conservation planning tool to support decision-making regarding the design of terrestrial, marine, and/or aquatic reserves and management areas. It produces objective and transparent outcomes, enhancing participative planning and stakeholder engagement. It integrates various types of information and enables the development of sophisticated planning.

Tool name	MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
Overall Weaknesses	Poor data quality and quantity significantly impact outputs. Other significant weaknesses include the absence of a temporal dimension, large spatial information requirements, and increased processing time in complex planning scenarios and extensive areas. Moreover, targets must be determined based on expert opinion.

Simple assessment index

Simple assessment indices are methods for classifying marine systems according to human pressures and include those focusing on the primary community structural variables (abundance, species richness, and biomass) and derived community structural variables (such as diversity indices, abundance and biomass ratios, and evenness indices). Functional analyses, including those involving feeding guilds and responses to organic matter inputs or other human pressures, are also part of these indices, often referred to as “biotic indices”. There are numerous biotic indices covering different biological elements, including phytoplankton, zooplankton, macroalgae, seagrasses, macroinvertebrates and fishes. Among these, indices using several metrics (e.g., richness, diversity, proportion of opportunistic/sensitive species, etc.) and combined in different ways (e.g., multimetric, multivariate) have been very successful (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Simple assessment index (generic tool, #17) [3 responses; 2 Expert, 1 Very familiar].

Tool name		Simple assessment index (generic tool)
Tool group		Simple assessment index
Uses of the tool		
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (18, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*1.1) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*3) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*0.8) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*3.1) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*2.2) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*0.8) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*1.2) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.5) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*1.9) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.4) • EBM13 - Climate change (*0.7) 	

Tool name	Simple assessment index (generic tool)
Tool group	Simple assessment index
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*1.6) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*1.4) • EBM17 – Risks (*0.9) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.4) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM16 - Uncertainty <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements.</p> <p>A simple assessment index is usually limited to a specific aspect of the element being assessed, and by design, it cannot comprehensively cover all aspects on its own. Utilizing multiple simple indexes and other methods provides a more holistic view of the status or biodiversity parameters.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities • Water Framework Directive (WFD) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess GES criteria. Various criteria within D1 (Biodiversity), D2 (Non-indigenous species), D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish), D6 (Sea-floor integrity) (e.g., D6C3), D10 (Marine litter). Also, criteria linked to the WFD, such as D5C8.</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	

Tool name	
Simple assessment index (generic tool)	
Tool group	
Simple assessment index	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for use in most situations, except in data-poor and skills-poor situations, when it becomes moderately suited.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abundance, biomass, biovolume, age distribution, species count, body size, arrivals. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence/absence. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required. Spatial outputs are produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical

Tool name	Simple assessment index (generic tool)
Tool group	Simple assessment index
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytical Ecological knowledge <p>Overall, no specific software is required. Some assessment indices might require software (e.g., M-AMBI).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://ambi.azti.es/ Borja A., Mader J., Muxika I., Rodriguez J. G., Bald J., 2008. Using M-AMBI in assessing benthic quality within the Water Framework Directive: Some remarks and recommendations. Marine Pollution Bulletin, 56: 1377-1379
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way. Generally, reference conditions are needed to apply the tool. The simplicity of the tool means that the real world is represented in a very simple manner as well. This results in a coarse representation of the world but makes the indices manageable. For example, for AMBI and similar indices, types of species are assigned to species classes based on sensitivity.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No monitoring data available It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> While all countries/regions currently have monitoring programmes, it is desirable to extend these to fully cover their areas.
Overall Strengths	Simple and easy to understand, making it accessible for communication with stakeholders. Applicable in any location. There are numerous simple assessment indices, and they all can tell a story or address specific aspects of any issue.
Overall Weaknesses	The simplicity of the tool group can also be a weakness due to its highly sectoral approach. It demands extensive and potentially costly monitoring coverage, especially for tasks like benthic sampling. Typically, multiple indices are necessary to accurately describe the status. Furthermore, there is a requirement for establishing reference conditions.

Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models

The indicator-based multi-metric assessment tools integrate quantitative indicators to inform of the integrated state of the assessment area. Tools have been developed for hazardous substances (CHASE), eutrophication (HEAT), and biodiversity (BEAT). The indicators use a threshold value indicating the acceptable state from the unacceptable state, and the indicators can be grouped within the tool to best reflect the assessment topic. For example, in the integrated biodiversity assessment, habitat-related indicators are assessed together, while species population indicators are assessed in another group of indicators. The integration of the indicators is done on two levels: indicators within a group are first integrated by weighted averaging to derive a state of the group, and then (2) each of the groups is compared: the group with the worst state is selected to represent the integrated state of the area, following the precautionary principle (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool, #18) [2 responses; 1 Expert, 1 Very familiar].

Tool name	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool)
Tool group	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.4) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*4.8) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*3.3) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.3) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*2.5) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1.5) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1.6) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*4.8) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.5) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.6)

Tool name	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool)
Tool group	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.1) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (3.1) • EBM17 – Risks (1.4) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.9) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM13 - Climate change <p>Descriptor or theme-specific combinations of indices and models are able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements. Examples of tools considered: HEAT, BEAT, CHASE, and MESH tools.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess all GES descriptors and criteria. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1 (Biodiversity) • D5 (Eutrophication) • D8 (Contaminants in the environment)
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited for use in any data-rich situations. It is poorly suited for use in data-poor, skills-poor situations, but its suitability can be improved with an improvement in skills.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables

Tool name	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool)
Tool group	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends on the tool and purpose: e.g., pressure data in terms of concentrations of chemicals or abundance of species. For indicators, annual means plus target values are usually needed. Overall, the tools in this category span a wide range of possibilities. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends on the tool and purpose: e.g., pressure data in terms of categorised pressure levels of chemicals or abundance of species. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends on the tool and purpose, e.g., presence/absence of ecosystem components. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>No spatial components are required. Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., >100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) <p>HEAT, BEAT, CHASE-based assessments usually focus on specific assessment periods (5-6 years).</p>
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. There are two approaches: a simple expert-based ranking system and the system used in NEAT/WATERS.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Programming (e.g., R) • Ecological knowledge

Tool name	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool)
Tool group	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models
	<p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HELCOM, 2010. Ecosystem Health of the Baltic Sea 2003–2007: HELCOM Initial Holistic Assessment. Balt. Sea Environ. Proc. No. 122 • Andersen J.H., Carstensen J., Conley D.J., Dromph K., Fleming-Lehtinen V., Gustafsson B., Josefson A., Norkko A., Villnas A., Murray C., 2017. Long-term temporal and spatial trends in eutrophication status of the Baltic Sea. Biological Reviews 92: 135–149
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>One response reported that the tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable, while another response noted that integration principles, such as 'one-out, all-out' may influence the result, but this assumption does not (or is unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available <p>HEAT, BEAT, CHASE, MESH (and also NEAT, WATERS, MALT) are fundamentally rooted in the initial HEAT version adopted by HELCOM in the period of 2009-2010. The primary challenge has consistently been achieving acceptance.</p>
Overall Strengths	<p>Simple and easy to use, with wide applicability - HEAT (and spin-out tools) are now widely used in Europe.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>A broad generalising approach that disregards having all indicators in the same scale. The tools heavily rely on data, and in many locations/countries, particularly offshore, the inadequacy of monitoring compromises the ability to make robust assessments.</p>

Overarching assessment tools

Overarching assessment tools are used to combine a potentially broad range of individual indicators to produce an overall assessment of the ecosystem status. The indicators to combine may belong to different stages of the management cycle (e.g., the stages in DAPSI(W)R(M)). These tools typically compare the results of the indicators against a set of target or threshold values, and through various combination rules, the overall (integrated) compliance with the final target can be assessed. Combination rules can include weighted averages or more sophisticated rules such as decision trees, spatial threshold application or the one-out-all-out rule (e.g., employed in the European Water Framework Directive for biological quality elements). The rules may vary at different aggregation/integration levels of the overarching assessment. Some assessment tools include a hierarchy of indicators, which gives an implicit weighting of indicator results based on their level of aggregation in the hierarchy. The critical aspect of an overarching assessment tool is to combine highly diverse indicators in a meaningful and transparent manner.

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Overarching assessment tools (generic tool, #19) [4 responses; 2 Expert, 2 Very Familiar].
- NEAT (specific/particular tool, #19.1) [3 responses; 2 Expert, 1 Familiar].

Tool name		Overarching assessment tools (generic tool)
Tool group		Overarching assessment tools
Uses of the tool		
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.7) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*4.5) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*4.5) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*1.5) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*1.5) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.4) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*2.7) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*2.8) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*2.5) 	

Tool name	Overarching assessment tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*3.3) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.9) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*3.1) • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.9) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.5) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*3.7) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*4) • EBM17 – Risks (*0.7) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*3) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Most respondents (75%) considered that the tool is able to fully deliver the above EBM elements. The remaining respondents considered that the tool needs to fulfil pressure assessment. They noted that the tool needs to incorporate pressure assessment. They also highlighted that the tool does not cover all the PACE management phases and requires upgrades to accommodate PACE requirements, such as Plan and Act.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • For official EU MSFD reporting • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess all GES descriptors and criteria, but it is typically used for D1 (Biodiversity), D5 (Eutrophication) and D6 (Sea-floor integrity).</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor and skills-poor situations.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables

Tool name	Overarching assessment tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as single variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptor indicators (e.g., nutrients) - both synoptic monitoring data and target values (for NEAT). <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk-based approaches. Semi-quantitative data can, in principle, be used but are typically transferred to a quantitative scale. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observation notes, semi-structured interviews, concept maps, case studies. Qualitative data are typically transferred to a quantitative scale using some assumptions. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>No spatial components are required. Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)

Tool name		Overarching assessment tools (generic tool)	
Tool group		Overarching assessment tools	
		The requirements depend on the tool: it may require spatial input (OHI) or not (NEAT). In the latter case, NEAT will still apply to a specific spatial area. Also, NEAT can be based on modelling and be used for forecasting.	
Confidence/Uncertainty		<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. Standard errors of indicators should be provided, or they can be computed with access to monitoring data. However, not all tools allow this functionality (NEAT/WATERS/BEAT2.0 all include confidence assessment).</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. Not all tools have this functionality, but NEAT, for example, has it built-in. All measures produced are based on Monte Carlo calculations.</p>	
Other resources required		<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>	
Tool references/links		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://oceanhealthindex.org/ 	
Strengths and Weaknesses			
Limitations to tool applicability		Most of the responses (75%) reported that the tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable. However, it was noted that integration principles used by some tools, such as 'one-out-all-out', may influence the result, but this assumption does not (or is unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability.	
Barriers to tool application		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available 	
Overall Strengths		Wide applicability, overarching approach with confidence assessment. NEAT/WATERS/BEAT2.0 are state of the art and used by researchers, competent authorities, as well as HELCOM and EEA.	
Overall Weaknesses		The tool typically requires a significant amount of input data. It does not account for ecological interactions. Data cannot be entered in bulk, and it does not keep a history of entries in the database. A wider acceptance is desired.	

Tool name	NEAT (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18.1 - Other policy requirements - MSPD • EBM18.2 - Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives • EBM 18.3 - Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Most respondents (66%) considered that other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. The tool requires improved spatial integration, and the links between activity-pressure, pressure-impacts, and impacts-ecosystem services are not explicitly established (conclusions can be drawn, but this is not explicit). The assessment of ecosystem services could be achieved if the tool is adapted.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within other National Competent Authorities • Specific projects (impact assessment) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc.

Tool name	NEAT (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1 (Biodiversity) • D2 (Non-indigenous species) • D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish) • D5 (Eutrophication) • D6 (Sea-floor integrity) • D8 (Contaminants in the environment) • D9 (Contaminants in seafood) <p>It requires adapting for assessing criteria.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	Overall, the tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor and skills-poor situations. One response considered the tool well-suited for all situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measured values: biota mortality, biota biomass, pollutant concentrations, nutrient concentrations. Indicator values and standard errors (e.g., temporal data, spatial area). Preferably long-time data series. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species, seagrass distribution. Assigns approximate measurements to data: biotic index. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitats, threatened species. Surveys, observation notes. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>

Tool name	NEAT (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>NEAT does not require maps, but requires information on the area to which each indicator is applied (this was considered here as spatial data). It also requires temporal data to produce indicators with associated standard error; otherwise, the assessment cannot be carried out. Spatial outputs refer to assessments done for Spatial Assessment Units (SAUs), while temporal outputs refer to the assessments done for a specific time. Furthermore, if done in different years, it provides a temporal series of assessments.</p>
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. NEAT automatically calculates confidence (uncertainty) using Monte Carlo simulations.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
<p>Tool references/links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.azti.es/productos/neat/ • Berg T., Murray C., Carstensen J., Andersen J.H., 2018. NEAT – Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool. Manual version 1.4. 38pp. • Frascchetti S., Fabbrizzi E., Tamburello L., Uyarra M. C., Micheli F., Sala E., Pipitone C., Badalamenti F., Bevilacqua S., Boada J., Cebrian E., Ceccherelli G., Chiantore M., D'Anna G., Di Franco A., Farina Si., Giakoumi S., Gissi E., Guala I., Guidetti P., Katsanevakis S., Manea E., Montefalcone M., Sini M., Asnaghi Va., Calo A., Di Lorenzo M., Garrabou J., Musco L., Oprandi A., Rilov G., Borja A., 2022. An integrated assessment of the Good Environmental Status of

Tool name	NEAT (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
	Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas, Journal of Environmental Management, 305, 114370.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable. Users have the flexibility to make assumptions when applying the tool, such as assigning equal weight to all ecosystem components or using different weights.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • It requires good ecological understanding to interpret adequately both inputs and outputs <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In situations with limited data, effective interpretation is crucial. • In situations with limited skills, the tool is not complex to learn, and training would be sufficient.
Overall Strengths	NEAT provides an integrative evaluation of ecological status, aligning seamlessly with MSFD assessment requirements. It is easy to learn, free, and uses hierarchical integration. The tool incorporates uncertainty and is suitable for data-poor areas, though careful interpretation of results is necessary. NEAT has the potential for adaptation to other assessments. It is a holistic integration assessment that considers spatial and temporal scales, employs an ecosystem-based approach, and identifies environmental issues requiring management attention and corresponding measures.
Overall Weaknesses	NEAT cannot integrate indicators based on expert knowledge or present-absence data. It cannot import data from Excel. It lacks the capability to produce "map" outputs. It would need adaptation to meet the new MSFD (criteria assessment, functional groups assessments, etc.). Targets/thresholds are necessary, and cumulative impact assessment is still pending. Sometimes, errors occur that are difficult to identify.

Size spectrum models

Size-spectrum models are physiologically-structured models that provide a way of investigating the structure and dynamics of complex ecological communities through the distribution of abundance or biomass against the body size of individuals on a log–log scale. The use of the body size is a central feature of these models because this trait correlates strongly with several biological processes, including metabolism, predator-prey relations, encounter rates, functional responses, reproductive effort, and other vital rates. Overall, there are three model types that differ in their degree of complexity: the food-web, the trait-based and the community models. The size spectrum approach offers several advantages, including the use of a limited number of parameters, minimal computational requirements, and a robust mechanistic basis, providing a framework of low to intermediate complexity. This framework is particularly well-suited for assessing the impact of pressures such as fishing and environmental changes on marine ecosystems (Andersen et al., 2015).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Size spectrum models (generic tool, #20) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Size spectrum models (generic)
Tool group	Size spectrum models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>The tool is not considered to address any EBM elements (and consequently any PACE management phases) in its current state because the tool is not currently being used.</p> <p>After further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address the following EBM elements: (8, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan

Tool name		Size spectrum models (generic)	
Tool group		Size spectrum models	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Adequate size spectrum models, such as the Non-Linear Species Size Spectrum Model, have been demonstrated to predict real size spectra over a wide parameter range to a management-relevant accuracy. They also predict the relevant time scales of dynamics.</p>	
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management		<p>The tool is not currently being used.</p> <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds 	
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed		<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish) • D1C3; D1C6 • D4C3 	
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs			
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation		<p>The tool is well-suited for use in skills-rich situations and moderately suited in skills-poor situations.</p>	
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool		<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as single variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables 	
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components		<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures on populations in the form of changes in mortality or respiration rate. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Size-spectrum models convert pressures on ecosystems into size-spectrum responses.</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>	
Spatial and temporal scales		<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data).</p>	

Tool name		Size spectrum models (generic)	
Tool group		Size spectrum models	
		Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) 	
Confidence/Uncertainty		The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.	
Other resources required		Expertise required to apply the tool: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelling • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>	
Tool references/links		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rossberg, A.G., Gaedke, U. and Kratina, P., 2019. Dome patterns in pelagic size spectra reveal strong trophic cascades. Nature communications, 10(1), p.4396. 	
Strengths and Weaknesses			
Limitations to tool applicability		The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.	
Barriers to tool application		No additional potential barriers to application.	
Overall Strengths		Size-spectrum models have always been studied because of their potential use in ecosystem management and because of their intrinsically low data requirements, robustness and transparency. The problem, until recently, was just that the proposed models were too simple to reproduce observed phenomenology. The non-linear SSM has overcome these problems.	
Overall Weaknesses		Size-spectrum models inevitably make simplifying assumptions that limit the accuracy of their predictions. They will, therefore, not be able to reproduce a detailed ecosystem state. However, at the level of detail required for GES descriptors, this is not an issue.	

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